

STREAMLINED **GERIATRIC** AND **ONCOLOGICAL** EVALUATION BASED ON IC **TECHNOLOGY**
 FOR HOLISTIC PATIENT-ORIENTED HEALTHCARE MANAGEMENT
 FOR OLDER MULTIMORBID PATIENTS

HORIZON 2020 PROGRAMME – TOPIC H2020-SC1-BHC-24-2020
 Start date: 01/04/2021 - Duration: 60 months

**D3.1: LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE COST-EFFECTIVENESS OF
 SERVICE INTERVENTION FOR OLDER MULTIMORBID PATIENTS**

Lead Beneficiary: 8-BOC

Involved Beneficiaries: 1-UBx; 4-DIAK

Primary author(s)	Lucia, Ferrara; Vittoria, Ardito; Valeria D., Tozzi, Rosanna Tarricone BOC
Deliverable Type	Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Due Date	2022-03-31 (M12)
Pages	49
Document version	V5
Project Acronym	GERONTE
Project Title	Streamlined Geriatric and Oncological evaluation based on IC Technology for holistic patient-oriented healthcare management for older multimorbid patients
Grant Agreement Number	945218
Project Coordinator	Université de Bordeaux Prof. Pierre SOUBEYRAN

GERONTE Consortium

Number	Participant Name	Short Name	Country
1	Université de Bordeaux <i>LTP1 : CHU Bordeaux</i> <i>LTP2 : Institut Bergonié</i>	UBx CHU Bx IB	FR
2	Katholieke Universitat Leuven	KUL	BE
3	Stichting Diaconessenhuis	DIAK	NL
4	Oslo University Hospital	OUS	NO
5	University College Dublin	UCD	IE
6	E-Seniors	ESE	FR
7	MyPL SAS	MyPL	FR
8	Università Luigi Bocconi	BOC	IT
9	International Society of Geriatric Oncology	SIOG	CH
10	Dublin City University	DCU	IE

Università Commerciale
Luigi Bocconi

Disclaimer and acknowledgment

Copyright ©CCBY 4.0, all rights reserved. This report is subject to a disclaimer and copyright. This report has been carried out under grant agreement [No. 945218](#) from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. The sole responsibility for the content of this project lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made

Contributors

Contributor	Participant
Lucia Ferrara	BOC – Participant 8
Vittoria Ardito	BOC – Participant 8
Valeria D. Tozzi	BOC – Participant 8
Rosanna Tarricone	BOC – Participant 8

History of Changes

Version	Date	Author	Description of change
V1.0	2022-02-01	Vittoria Ardito	First draft
V2.0	2022-03-01	Lucia Ferrara	Feedback on first draft
V3.0	2022-03-15	Valeria D. Tozzi	Manuscript review
V3.1	2022-03-15	Rosanna Tarricone	Manuscript review
V4.0	2022-03-31	Lucia Ferrara, Vittoria Ardito	Implementation of suggested changes and final reading
V5.0	2023-02-06	Lucia Ferrara, Vittoria Ardito	Implementation of changes suggested by the EC after the first periodic report

Table of Content

Executive Summary	5
1. Introduction to Deliverable 3.1	8
1.1 GERONTE and its objectives	8
1.2 Rationale.....	8
2. Literature review on economic evaluations of healthcare service interventions for older multimorbid patients.....	9
2.1 Introduction.....	9
Background.....	9
Objectives.....	10
2.2 Methods	10
Study design	10
Selection criteria.....	10
Information sources	11
Search strategy	11
Study selection	11
Data extraction	11
Consultation with experts	12
2.3 Results	13
Overview of Economic Evaluations of health service interventions	13
Methods of Economic Evaluations of health service interventions.....	22
2.4 Discussion	25
Summary of evidence.....	25
Limitations.....	26
2.5 Conclusion	27
3. Bibliography.....	28
Annexe 1: Key word search strategy	34
Annexe 2: Workshops.....	35
Annexe 3: Dissemination activities.....	40

Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the results of Task 3.1 “Literature review on the cost-effectiveness of service intervention for older multimorbid patients”, developed as part of Work Package 3 activities which support GERONTE’s objective 3: Develop socio-economic methods for evaluating the impacts of the implementation of the GERONTE intervention and more specifically O3.3 “Develop a model to perform economic evaluation of complex healthcare services”.

The contents of this Deliverable are summarized hereafter.

Introduction/Context

Patients with multiple morbidities have been growing significantly due to the aging population, which translates in an equally exponential increase in healthcare costs and patterns of resource utilization across resource types including medication, primary care, and outpatient visits, as well as emergency department presentations and hospitalisations (both frequency of admissions and bed days occupied). Despite the expansion of multimorbidity worldwide, and an increasing amount of empirical research conducted to inform the allocation of scarce healthcare resources at various levels, there is still a scarcity of cost-effectiveness evaluation for chronic disease interventions originating from patient samples with multimorbidity and the approaches to the evaluation of the quality of care for people with multimorbidity frequently relies on aggregating disease-specific indicators for the quality of processes and outcomes of care which are typically derived from single-disease-oriented guidelines.

Objectives

Based on this premises this work aims at identifying recent economic evaluation of service interventions that target multimorbid patients, with the goals to either identify methods and models that can be applied to the evaluation of GERONTE, and to highlight methodological gaps in available publications.

Methods

We conducted a scoping literature review of papers published between 2010 and 2021 (June) on Pub Med, Science Direct, EconLit and Web Of Science. We looked at economic evaluations of service interventions targeting patients with at least two chronic conditions and delivered through multiple care setting (including digital channel).

Results

Twenty-nine relevant articles were included in the review. This review highlights growing academic attention towards cost-effectiveness analysis of service interventions targeting multimorbid patients. However, most of the studies on chronic conditions are still single-disease centred and multimorbidity is still analysed as the combination of two or more specific health conditions (e.g., COPD + depression), as opposed to an omni-comprehensive status. There is limited evidence on economic evaluations on service interventions designed for oncologic patients, especially geriatric patients with cancer. Lastly, most service interventions assessed through this review are delivered in specific care settings, and their evidence is poorly transferable to other contexts.

Conclusions

The evidence from the literature review allowed to identify current gaps in the literature surrounding the evaluation of multimorbid care pathway and to provide insight on how the GERONTE model and the economic evaluation planned within GERONTE Project can fulfil these gaps.

Deliverable work status

Deliverable	Completion status in %	Deviation	Data complete or to be updated
D3.1 Literature review on the cost-effectiveness of healthcare services for older multimorbid patients	100 %	None	100%
Associated Deliverables	D3.2 Definition of the protocol for economic evaluation of GerOnTe		
Associated Objectives	O3.3 “Develop a model to perform economic evaluation of complex healthcare services”		

Description of deliverable

This deliverable describes the evidence from a scoping literature review, aimed at identifying recent economic evaluation of service interventions that target multimorbid patients, with the goals to either identify methods and models that can be applied to the evaluation of GerOnTe. The evidence from the literature review allowed to identify current gaps in the literature surrounding the evaluation of multimorbid care pathway and to provide insight on how the GERONTE model and the economic evaluation planned within GERONTE Project can be carried out and fill some of these gaps.

This deliverable is connected to D3.2, “Definition of the protocol for economic evaluation of GerOnTe”, and can therefore be considered preparatory for the later drafting of the protocol for the economic evaluation. The literature review, in fact, allowed us to understand how similar health interventions are assessed, and if there are any gaps in the evaluation methods.

The deliverable is associated to WP3 objective related to identifying existing methods and models for economic evaluation of healthcare services that can be applied to the evaluation of GerOnTe.

Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations

The objectives related to this deliverable have been achieved in full and as described in Annexe 1 (Description of the Action Part A) of the Grant Agreement N°945218.

Justification for delay in deliverable submission

The objectives related to this deliverable have been achieved on time and as scheduled in Annexe 1 (Description of the Action Part A) of the Grant Agreement N°945218

Data associated

The objective, methods and results of the literature review conducted under Task 3.1 are described in detail in Deliverable 3.1, deposited at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7688696>. The dataset relating to this task can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7137717>.

1. Introduction to Deliverable 3.1

1.1 GERONTE and its objectives

GERONTE is a 5-year research and innovation project (April 2021 to March 2026) funded by the European Union within the framework of the H2020 Research and Innovation programme, in response to the health societal challenge topic SC1-BHC-24-2020 “Healthcare interventions for the management of the elderly multimorbid patient”. The overall aim of GERONTE is to improve quality of life - defined as well-being on three levels: global health status, physical functioning and social functioning- for older multimorbid patients, while reducing overall costs of care. To this end, GERONTE will co-design, test, and prepare for deployment an innovative cost-effective patient-centred holistic health management system, hereafter referred to as the GERONTE intervention. GERONTE intervention will rely on an ICT based application for real-time collection and integration of standardised clinical and home patient-reported data. GERONTE intervention will be demonstrated in the context of care of multimorbid patients having cancer as a dominant morbidity, and be adaptable to any other combination of morbidities.

The objectives are the following:

O1: INFORMATION gather the stakeholders and data needed for patient-centred and multi-actor complex decision-making process and management

O2: TOOLS develop ICT tools for the GERONTE intervention to be implemented

O3: METHODS develop socio-economic methods for evaluating the impacts of the implementation of the GERONTE intervention

O4: DEMONSTRATION demonstrate in 16 study sites from three EU countries the feasibility and effectiveness of the GERONTE intervention

O5: REPLICATION develop recommendations for the replication of GERONTE best practices in all European health systems

O6: ENGAGEMENT engage all stakeholders by co-designing the GERONTE intervention

1.2 Rationale

Deliverable 3.1 is the output of Task 3.1 “Literature review on the cost-effectiveness of service intervention for older multimorbid patients”, as part of Work Package 3 activities which support GERONTE’s objective 3 “Develop socio-economic methods for evaluating the impacts of the implementation of the GERONTE intervention”, and more specifically O3.3 “Develop a model to perform economic evaluation of complex healthcare services”. This work has been performed independently by Bocconi (BOC), while DIAK, UBx and KUL provided a support in identifying potential challenges related to the specific contexts. The evidence from this review is intended to inform the draft of the protocol of the economic evaluation (Task 3.2; Deliverable 3.2).

2. Literature review on economic evaluations of healthcare service interventions for older multimorbid patients

2.1 Introduction

Background

That people affected by multimorbidity are rapidly growing in number comes as no surprise. Over the years, scientific progress and advancements in the life sciences improved health outcomes, resulting in people being healthier and living longer. However, with age it is common to develop chronic conditions, and in those aged 65 to 84, the proportion of patients with multimorbidity is as high as 65% and rises to 81% in those aged 85 or older¹. Multimorbidity has multiple definitions, however it is commonly defined as the presence of multiple diseases or conditions². Multimorbidity translates in an equally exponential increase in healthcare costs and patterns of resource utilization across resource types including medication^{3,4}, primary care and outpatient specialist occasions of service^{5,6}, as well as emergency department presentations and hospitalisations⁷, both in terms of frequency of admissions and bed days occupied. As such, there is agreement that multimorbidity is a concern for the potential budget impact and for the sustainability for healthcare systems.

Developing appropriate solutions for the management of multimorbid patients becomes crucial to improve care of vulnerable patients, while maximizing the use of healthcare resources. Despite their growing magnitude both in volume and societal impact, currently acute-hospital care is still mainly single-disease oriented and coexisting morbidities are often under-evaluated and under-managed leading to inappropriate admissions, suboptimal care, and unnecessary costs. As a result, the approaches to the evaluation of the quality of care for people with multimorbidity still consider the quality of care as the sum of disease-specific indicators for each condition and focus on individual domain rather than bringing them together as of a comprehensive framework. Also cost-effectiveness studies focused on chronic disease interventions targeting multimorbid patients seem to be scarce⁸. Indeed, while methods for conducting economic evaluations (EE) of drugs and medical devices are well established, to date economic evaluations focused on health services interventions designed for multimorbid patients have not received comparable attention. Multimorbidity itself raises methodological and pragmatic challenges, to the extent that replicating standard economic evaluation methods is just not feasible. The multidisciplinary nature of multimorbidity care pathways makes it harsh to capture all relevant data on costs and impact. Due to the chronic nature of most diseases, the “time factor” becomes pivotal, as costs tend to increase over time. The frailty of multimorbid patients raises equity issues related either to properly evaluating health benefits for older segments, or to not misrepresenting them in clinical trials. Under representation of certain morbidity profiles in clinical trials has been extensively discussed⁹. For instance, patients suffering from cancer or who survived prior malignancies are typically excluded from trial studies¹⁰, especially older and comorbid populations. Another challenge relates to the transferability of the evidence from EEs. Evidence from EEs conducted so far are highly dependent from the setting where each intervention is being tested. This limitation combined with the high fragmentation of healthcare systems^(11,12) and the limited interoperability of healthcare systems and data¹³, make the evidence from EEs poorly transferrable to other contexts.

In this context, GERONTE main concept is to propose a major step-change from a fragmented system of care to a more integrated and coordinated care pathway for older multimorbid patients that aims to achieve the triple aim¹⁴: improve quality of life, improve experience of care and reduce costs. To

this end, GERONTE will co-design, test, and prepare for deployment an innovative cost-effective patient-centred holistic health management system which will be demonstrated in the context of care of multimorbid patients having cancer as a dominant morbidity, and be adaptable to any other combination of morbidities. Moreover, GERONTE ambition is to integrate the socio-economic dimension since the design of the research and to evaluate the cost-effectiveness and cost-utility of the model.

Objectives

This Task is aimed at identifying recent economic evaluations of service intervention that target multimorbid patients, with the goals to either identify methods and models that can be applied to the evaluation of GERONTE, and to highlight methodological gaps in available publications. Specifically, the analysis will focus on the characteristics of the service intervention tailored for multimorbid patients and on the methods currently used to conduct economic evaluations of health service interventions, including how to assess the average cost of care at the patient level, patients' satisfaction, health outcomes (i.e. patients' reported outcomes and patients' reported experience), quality of life and the cost-effectiveness of patient-centred health systems, as well as on the strengths and weaknesses of current outcome measures.

The evidence from this review will ultimately inform the protocol for the economic evaluation of GERONTE, with the goal of demonstrating its cost-effectiveness in the context of care of multimorbid patients having cancer as a dominant morbidity.

2.2 Methods

Study design

This work is a scoping review developed based on the updated methodological guidance for scoping reviews¹⁵, and it follows the PRISMA-ScR checklist for scoping reviews, containing 22 items¹⁶. The reasons for structuring this work with a scoping design mainly relate to its ambition to address a broad research question and to identify gaps in current methods. Indeed, scoping reviews are an appropriate methodology to map and summarize relevant concepts and research gaps in a given area of study by extensively identifying, reviewing, and synthesizing the information available in the literature,¹⁷ to inform future research. The scoping review design is also deemed particularly helpful since the literature surrounding chronic and multimorbid conditions is complex and heterogeneous. This study was not registered on any databases for scoping reviews.

Selection criteria

Economic evaluations, either full or partial, of health service interventions for multi-morbid patients were searched. Although there are multiple definitions of multimorbidity, we defined it as the simultaneous presence of 2 or more disease conditions¹⁸, and we set this definition as a stringent inclusion criterion. We did not set any age limit on the study participants and did not limit our analysis to geriatric patients only, because multi-morbidity typically increases with age¹⁹, with the mean age of the patients included in studies on (multiple) chronic conditions being typically relatively high. We did not exclude literature reviews (systematic reviews, scoping reviews, rapid reviews) ex ante from our search to check the reference list but did not eventually include them among our review papers.

Information sources

Relevant articles were searched in four electronic databases, namely PUB MED, SCIENCE DIRECT, ECONLIT and WEB OF SCIENCE. Studies were searched between January 2010 and the beginning of June 2021. The starting period was set in 2010 because of the amplified attention posed by international entities (e.g., WHO or the resolutions of the European Union¹) towards improving quality of care for older chronic people. We also adopted a “snowball” technique to include other relevant studies identified either by screening the reference lists (bibliographies of included studies), through manual electronic browsing (e.g., Googling) or searching specific websites and grey literature.

Search strategy

The keywords to be included in the search strategy were defined through an exploratory search. The exploratory search consisted in a quick literature search preparatory for the larger, more structured review of the literature. The search strategy was set based on three macro content areas, namely i) health service interventions, ii) multimorbidity and iii) economic evaluation. We applied the same search string for the 4 databases, while we tailored the search query to the specific requirements of each database. For instance, the PUB MED search was conducted using the following set of keywords in title/abstract: [(service intervention) OR (care pathway) OR (patient journey) OR (care program)] AND [(multimorbidity OR multimorbid OR comorbidity OR comorbid OR (chronic disease))] AND [(economic evaluation) OR methods OR (cost-effectiveness) OR (cost-utility) OR (cost-benefit)]. As indicated, a conventional Boolean search built on MeSH terminology was carried out, as opposed to performing a more advanced search developed on more sophisticated algorithms, with the rationale being that this conventional search was fit for the purposes of this work, namely exploring gaps in the methods used to conduct economic evaluations by conducting a scoping review of the literature. We did not initially impose a filter based on language of publication, but eventually only selected studies written in English. Moreover, no filter was set on country of publication. Relevant article type included literature reviews or research articles. All the results were imported into Zotero, a bibliographic reference manager. Additional details of the search string can be found in Annexe 1.

Study selection

The selection of the studies was conducted by two primary researchers (V.A. and L.F.), with two other reviewers (R.T. and V.T.). Studies were initially screened based on title and abstract by one researcher (V.A.). The articles that were deemed eligible for full text reading were then analyzed independently by two researchers (V.A. and L.F.). Disagreements on the inclusion/exclusion of a given study were jointly discussed and eventually solved with two other reviewers (R.T. and V.T.). Considering the high variety of the selected studies, both in terms of chronic condition treated and study design, we did not deem necessary to perform a quality check of the paper selected in the review.

Data extraction

Data extraction was performed on Excel based on a predefined extraction sheet form. First, a general overview of the selected studies was extracted, including title, abstract, country, journal of publication, publication year, aim of the study, and study design. In addition, any information about the health service intervention was retrieved, including the description of the intervention, the study setting and

¹ As a reference example, refer to the European Parliament resolution of 9 September 2010 on long-term care for older people (2011/C 308 E/13) where the European Parliament calls on Member State to recognise the importance of both the quality and continuity of care and to improve, facilitate, and encourage the development of specialist training, eHealth and service delivery model for older patients

target population, any relevant chronic conditions treated, and the multidisciplinary team of health care professionals. For certain study designs, like RCTs and observational studies, outcomes measure were also considered, namely the primary and secondary outcomes of the study, as well as the related metrics used. Lastly, specific information of economic evaluations (EEs) was extracted. These included the categorization between full EEs vs. partial EEs, the type of economic evaluation (e.g., Cost-Effectiveness Analysis, Cost-Utility Analysis, Cost-Benefit Analysis), outcome measures, cost measures, ICER, the perspective of the evaluation, sensitivity analysis.

Table 1 provides an overview of the methods and choices made.

Table 1 - Methods

Study design	Scoping review
Information sources	4 databases: Pub Med, Science Direct, EconLit, Web of Science
Search strategy	Keywords to be included have been identified based on an exploratory search
Keyword search	(service intervention) OR (care pathway) OR (patient journey) OR (care program) AND (multimorbidity OR multimorbid OR comorbidity OR comorbid OR (chronic disease)) AND (economic evaluation) OR methods OR (cost-effectiveness) OR (cost-utility) OR (cost-benefit)
Time frame	10+ years (2010-2021 June)
Inclusion criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Studies published in medium- and high-income countries ▪ Study design: research articles and protocols related to observational studies, trials ▪ Single service interventions ▪ All target age, except for paediatric patients ▪ Multi-morbidity and care delivery through multiple setting
Exclusion criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Studies published in low-income countries ▪ Literature reviews and meta-analysis ▪ Single setting of care ▪ Intervention targeting paediatric patients

Consultation with experts

Following the Arksey and O'Malley¹⁷ methodological framework for scoping review we adopted a consultation methodology in order to collect qualitative insights from the clinical partners (UBx, DIAK and KUL) involved in the project, one from each Country involved in the trial. In details, we organized three online workshops of one hour one with each partner (See Annex 2 for more details on the workshops), following the same structure. During each workshop, the researchers from BOC provided an overview of the results of the literature review subsequently soliciting responses from UBx, DIAK and KUL about i) the specificities of health care delivery services that could help us better understand the resource used and related costs in Belgium, France and the Netherlands and ii) what are the distinctive features of service and delivery interventions that may pose challenges to the economic analysis of the GerOnTe model. These workshops complemented the information we found in the literature and were also useful to collect information about which symptoms and PROMs are relevant for our target patients during real-time patient reporting.

2.3 Results

Overview of Economic Evaluations of health service interventions

PRISMA diagram

The search yielded a total of 803 potentially relevant papers identified from the search (Figure 1). After duplicates were removed (n=47), the remaining were screened based on titles and abstracts (n=756). This preliminary screening identified n= 639 records that were not relevant for the purposes of our review and that were consequently excluded, leaving a pool of 117 publications to be assessed with full text reading. Reasons for exclusions were mainly due to the focus on a single chronic condition or to the study design (e.g., other literature reviews). A total of n=29 relevant studies were identified based on full-text reading. The results presented hereafter are therefore based on this final subset of articles.

Figure 1 Flowchart of study selection – PRISMA Diagram

Characteristics of the studies

Except for 2014, there were relevant studies every year between 2010 and 2021, with peaks in 2016 and 2020. Of the 29 studies selected, 9 were based in the UK^(20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28), 11 in European Union countries – 5 in Spain^(29,30,31,32,33), 3 in Germany^(34,35,36), 1 in Denmark⁽³⁷⁾, 1 in Ireland⁽³⁸⁾ and 1 in the Netherlands⁽³⁹⁾ – 4 in Canada^(40,41,42,43), 2 in the United States^(44,45), 2 in Australia^(46,47) and 1 in UAE⁽⁴⁸⁾.

59% of the studies are research article, whereas 41% are research protocols. Regarding study design, most of the studies are randomized controlled trial (RCT).

Table 2 presents an overview of the 29 papers included in the analysis, summarizing the year of publication, the country, the study design and the type of study.

Table 2 General overview of selected studies

Study	Year	Country	Study design	Type of study
Aragones et al. ²⁹	2020	Spain	RCT	Research article
Belnap et al. ⁴⁴	2019	USA	RCT	Research article
Piera-Jiménez et al. ³⁰	2021	Spain	Quasi-experimental study	Research article
Baynouna et al. ⁴⁸	2010	UAE	Quasi-experimental study	Research article
Schmidt et al. ³⁴	2017	Germany	Quasi-experimental study	Research article
Evans et al. ²⁰	2011	UK	RCT	Research article
Duarte et al. ²¹	2015	UK	RCT	Research article
Thorn et al. ²²	2020	UK	RCT	Research article
Henderson et al. ²³	2013	UK	RCT	Research article
Maru et al. ⁴⁷	2018	Australia	RCT	Research article
Russo et al. ⁴⁵	2012	USA	RCT	Research article
Camacho et al. ²⁴	2016	UK	RCT	Research article
Nobis et al. ³⁵	2013	Germany	RCT	Protocol
Rose et al. ³⁶	2015	Germany	RCT	Protocol
Casanas et al. ³¹	2019	Spain	RCT	Protocol
Pedersen et al. ³⁷	2021	Denmark	RCT	Protocol
Martin-Lesende et al. ³²	2011	Spain	RCT	Protocol
Shakib et al. ⁴⁶	2016	Australia	Cohort study	Research article
Bower et al. ²⁵	2012	UK	RCT	Protocol
Gray et al. ⁴⁰	2016	Canada	RCT	Protocol
Herkert et al. ³⁹	2020	The Netherlands	Quasi-experimental study	Protocol
Johnson et al. ⁴¹	2012	Canada	RCT	Protocol
Man et al. ²⁶	2016	UK	RCT	Protocol
Wanat et al. ²⁷	2017	UK	Cohort study	Protocol
Miklavcic et al. ⁴²	2020	Canada	RCT	Research article
Lanzeta et al. ³³	2016	Spain	RCT	Protocol
Weber et al. ⁴³	2012	Canada	RCT	Research article
Gillespie et al. ³⁸	2017	Ireland	RCT	Research article
Coventry et al. ²⁸	2015	UK	RCT	Research article

Conditions treated

The conditions more frequently included in the health service interventions targeting multimorbid patients are diabetes (type 1 or type 2) (12 studies – 41%), cardiovascular diseases (heart failure chronic or acute, ischemic heart disease, other) (12 studies – 41%), and mental disorders (depression or anxiety) (11 studies – 38%). There are cases where health service interventions are designed for a diversified pool of multimorbid target patients, regardless of their specific diseases. To date, only three studies target comorbid cancer patients^(34,21,27).

Table 3 Studies based on conditions treated

Study	Conditions treated									
	Mental disorders	Musculoskeletal conditions (pain)	Diabetes (type 1 or 2)	Hypertension	Cancer	Frailty	Chronic lung disease (COPD, asthma)	Irritable bowel syndrome	Cardiovascular diseases (HF chronic or acute, ischemic heart disease, other)	Other
Aragones, 2020 ²⁹	X - Depression	X								
Belnap, 2019 ⁴⁴	X - Depression								X	
Piera-Jiménez, 2021 ³⁰										several chronic conditions
Baynouna, 2010 ⁴⁸			X	X						
Schmidt, 2017 ³⁴					X					Geriatric comorbidities
Evans, 2011 ²⁰						X				X
Duarte, 2015 ²¹	X - Depression				X					
Thorn, 2020 ¹⁹										≥3 chronic conditions
Henderson, 2013 ²³			X				X		X	
Maru, 2018 ⁴⁷			X	X					X	
Russo, 2012 ⁴⁵	X - Depression		X						X	
Camacho, 2016 ²⁴	X - Depression		X						X	
Nobis, 2013 ³⁵	X - Depression		X							
Rose, 2015 ³⁶									X	+ 2 other conditions
Casanas, 2019 ³¹	X - Depression		X				X		X	
Pedersen, 2021 ³⁷	X - Depression								X	

Study	Conditions treated									
	Mental disorders	Musculoskeletal conditions (pain)	Diabetes (type 1 or 2)	Hypertension	Cancer	Frailty	Chronic lung disease (COPD, asthma)	Irritable bowel syndrome	Cardiovascular diseases (HF chronic or acute, ischemic heart disease, other)	Other
Martin-Lesende, 2011 ³²							X		X	
Shakib, 2016 ⁴⁶										2 chronic conditions
Bower, 2012 ²⁵			X				X	X		
Gray, 2016 ⁴⁰										>2 chronic conditions
Herkert, 2020 ³⁹							X		X	
Johnson, 2012 ⁴¹	X - Depression		X							
Man, 2016 ²⁶										>3 chronic conditions
Wanat, 2017 ²⁷	X - Depression				X					
Miklavcic, 2020 ⁴²			X							>2 chronic conditions
Lanzeta, 2016 ³³										>2 chronic conditions
Weber, 2012 ⁴³			X						X	X
Gillespie, 2017 ³⁸										X
Coventry, 2015 ²⁸	X - Depression		X						X	
Total (N)	11	1	12	2	3	1	5	1	12	12
Total (%)	38%	3%	41%	7%	10%	3%	17%	3%	41%	41%

Characteristics of health service interventions

The interventions delivered through the studies of this review serve different purposes. Using the classification by Smith et al. (2016)⁴⁹ we distinguished interventions between organizational-type interventions and patient-oriented interventions. The former involves case management, coordination of care or the enhancement of skill mix in multidisciplinary teams in addition to delivery of patient care; the latter includes psychoeducational programs, as well as individual or group-based sessions aimed at enhancing self-management and self-efficacy. Out of the 29 studies selected in this review, two-thirds fall into the organizational-type intervention, while the remaining one-third of the studies belongs to the patient-oriented interventions. However, health service interventions are often developed across multiple dimensions (e.g., a nurse care manager coordinates the health care efforts of different professionals, digital tools are used for patient monitoring, etc.), therefore they cannot be considered silos and easily clustered into a single dimension. While some interventions unambiguously fall within one or the other category, in some cases aspects from both classes coexist^(42,28).

The organizational complexity of health care interventions for chronic, multimorbid patients is also observed using a six-dimension framework developed by Ferrara et al. (forthcoming)⁵⁰:

- **Process management:** Tools and resources that focus on the patient journey and aim to analyze, define, optimize, and monitor care processes for driving improved performance of interdependent processes;
- **Data analytics:** Data collection, use of data and artificial intelligence to support decision making and draw conclusions;
- **Integrated service delivery:** Design and delivery of integrated health care services (e.g., Integrated practice unit or center) around a specific need or population;
- **ICT & Technology:** Covers the role of ICT and technology (mHealth, apps, eHealth) to impact on service delivery;
- **Human Resource Management:** Includes the collaboration between healthcare professionals and the workforce redesign to use resources more effectively and efficiently;
- **Financing:** Includes to move toward more value-based reimbursement schemes and strategies to reward providers for improving the coordination, quality and efficiency of care.

Based on this classification, we analysed which dimensions were included in the organizational-type interventions selected in this review (Table 4). We highlighted how improvement interventions often have an impact on several areas and dimensions at the same time. This confirms that improvements can be achieved if the entire care pathway for multimorbid patients from symptom onset to follow-up is considered.

Table 4 List of organizational-type interventions based on a 6-dimension framework

Study	Intervention	Process mgmt.	Data analytics	Integrated service delivery	ICT & Technology	HRM	Financing
Aragones, 2020 ²⁹	Clinical guideline into eHRs to guide GPs decisions	X	X				
Piera-Jiménez, 2021 ³⁰	ICT-enhanced integrated care model that enables tele monitoring, increasing the intensity of integrated care	X	X	X			
Baynouna, 2010 ⁴⁸	Structured care model with decision-making tools	X					
Schmidt, 2017 ³⁴	CGA: initial assessment and nurse aftercare by phone				X	X	
Evans, 2011 ²⁰	Palliative care by community-based multidisc specialists			X		X	
Thorn, 2020 ²²	Review of patients' health with nurse, pharmacist & GP					X	
Henderson, 2013 ²³	Risk-based alert system to trigger physician response	X	X				
Maru, 2018 ⁴⁷	Nurse-led care linked with home care and community HCP			X		X	
Rose, 2015 ³⁶	Medication review by pharmacists & home-care support			X		X	
Martin-Lesende, 2011 ³²	Tele monitoring intervention based on patient self-measurement & phone contacts with the doctor	X			X		
Shakib, 2016 ⁴⁶	Multidisciplinary assessment providing evidence-based recommendations, medicines review, outpatient follow-up		X			X	
Bower, 2012 ²⁵	Structured and patient-centred approach to the routine management of long-term conditions	X					
Herkert, 2020 ³⁹	Collection of PRO on a platform & monitoring by case manager	X			X		

Study	Intervention	Process mgmt.	Data analytics	Integrated service delivery	ICT & Technology	HRM	Financing
Johnson, 2012 ⁴¹	Collaborative care model aimed at reducing depressive symptoms			X		X	
Man, 2016 ²⁶	Replacing reviews of each disease with patient-centred ones	X		X			
Lanzeta, 2016 ³³	Improve communication bw/ PC & hospital professionals	X				X	
Weber, 2012 ⁴³	Integrated multidisciplinary care model			X		X	
Gillespie, 2017 ³⁸	How to conduct a GP-led medicines review with patients	X					
Miklavcic, 2020 ⁴²	In-home visits, group wellness program, case conferencing and care coordination	X		X		X	
Coventry, 2015 ²⁸	Management of drug treatment, and prevention of relapse	X					

For the patient-oriented intervention type, it is also possible to highlight how the service delivery often covers several dimensions at the same time (Table 5).

Table 5 List of patient-oriented intervention

Study	Intervention	Psycho-educational	Self-mgmt.	Self-efficacy
Belnap, 2019 ⁴⁴	Lifestyle modification, increasing medication adherence, monitoring symptom	X		
Duarte, 2015 ²¹	Provide information on depression, delivering psychological interventions and monitoring progress	X		
Russo, 2012 ⁴⁵	Enhance patient self-management, treatment intensification, coordination, and continuity of care		X	
Camacho, 2016 ²⁴	Evidence-based low-intensity psychological treatments	X		
Nobis, 2013 ³⁵	Web-based self-help program to address diabetes-specific aspects with online guided sessions		X	X
Casanas, 2019 ³¹	Weekly sessions on chronic pathology and depression; lifestyle; breathing techniques; behavioral activation; self-esteem and assertiveness	X		X
Pedersen, 2021 ³⁷	Support with sleep and lifestyle changes, and psychological tools through an online platform	X	X	
Gray, 2016 ⁴⁰	Improve patient self-management and shared decision-making between patients and HCP	X	X	
Wanat, 2017 ²⁷	Education on depression, evidence-based psychological treatments, patient progress monitoring	X		
Miklavcic, 2020 ⁴²	In-home visits, group wellness program, case conferencing and care coordination			X
Coventry, 2015 ²⁸	Behavioural activation, lifestyle advice, management of drug treatment, and prevention of relapse	X	X	X

Health care professionals (HCPs) involved

The delivery of health service interventions typically involves several health care professionals (HCPs) with structured care pathways. The HCPs by far most represented in delivering care for chronic patients are general practitioners (GPs) (16 studies – 55%) and nurses (20 studies – 69%). In some cases, nurses are trained by disease-area, especially for complex conditions that require a high-degree of specialization (e.g., oncology nurse). 5 studies (17%) involve specialty doctors, 6 studies (20%) pharmacists, and 15 studies (52%) involve other professionals, like psychologists, physiotherapists, dieticians, to name a few. Physicians, including primary care and specialty doctors, are typically engaged in a structured way, through dedicated protocols or platforms.

Care/case managers appear to be pivotal in patient-centred care models. They act as coordinators of the care pathway involving multiple professionals, with their primary focus being either on defining the necessary steps to recover, as well as organizing the care plan overall (case manager)⁶⁴, and on taking care of the patient alongside each touch point of pathway (care manager)⁵¹. 6 of the selected

studies (20%) have this profile, which in 50% of the cases is taken over by highly specialized and trained nurses, like cardiac or oncologic nurses.

Care settings

Lastly, we looked at the care settings where health service interventions for chronic multimorbid patients are delivered. Specifically, as care delivery through multiple settings was amongst the inclusion criteria, we assessed the combinations of different care settings. Primary care is by far the most common care setting (19 studies – 65%), followed by hospital (10 studies – 34%), home care (7 studies – 24%) and community setting (5 studies – 17%). Zooming in on hospital care, it is observed in combination with home care (4 studies), primary care (2 studies), outpatient care (1 study), community setting (1 study) and digital programs (1 study). Not surprisingly, delivering care interventions entails plenty of digital components in nearly every study considered in this review. Digital channels might be involved either as a core component to deliver the intervention, where the digital element is key, or as a mere communication or support channel. The former includes, but is not limited to, platforms for symptom monitoring, or Apps that enable for real-time, integrated patient-physician communication; on the other hand, the latter refers to an unstructured, not formalized use of the digital elements, like telephone follow-ups between clinicians and patients.

Outcome metrics

The outcome measures assessed in the selected studies were analysed, using the taxonomy for Core Outcome Set (COS) developed by Dodd⁵². This COS classifies outcome measures according to 5 core areas – namely Death; Physiological/clinical; Life impact; Resource use; Adverse events –, to each of which are associated various outcome domains (38 in total). Each of the core areas of the taxonomy are analysed in-depth hereafter. Table 6 provides an overview of the core outcome, the three top outcome domains for each core area and examples of outcome measures for each domain.

Life impact is by far the core area where most of the outcome metrics is observed. The evidence is not surprising, as health interventions targeting populations with chronic diseases commonly aim at improving patients' quality of care and, consequently, quality of life. Drilling down to the outcome domains, delivery of care, perceived health status and physical functioning are the ones observed with the higher frequency in the selected studies.

- Delivery of care includes outcomes like adherence/compliance, patient preferences, appropriateness of an intervention, accessibility, quality and adequacy of intervention, or patient/carer satisfaction. Examples of outcome measures gauged in the studies from our review are questionnaires to measure the satisfaction with care, or the Patient Assessment of Chronic Illness Care (PACIC) questionnaire⁵³;
- Perceived health status provides subjective ratings by the affected individual of their relative level of health. Within this category, quality of life (QoL) is by far the most extensively observed metric in the studies of our review. QoL is typically assessed by pairing a generic measure with a disease-specific one. EQ-5D⁵⁴ is the most common generic measure for quality of life;
- Physical functioning relates to the impact of a condition on the physical activities of daily living (for example, ability to walk, independence, self-care, performance status, disability index, motor skills, sexual dysfunction, health behaviour and management). In this case, an example is the Instrumental Activities of Daily Living scale (ADL)⁵⁵.

Physiological/clinical outcomes are also commonly observed. These outcomes figure either as primary or secondary endpoints, with their domain clearly varying depending on the disease conditions treated. Due to the common insurgence of mental health conditions in association with other chronic

diseases, psychiatric outcomes, such as the Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression (CESD-10)⁵⁶ scale or the “Depression-free days” questionnaire⁵⁷, are commonly observed.

Resource use – another COS core area that outlines determining elements of EEs – primarily includes metrics that fall within the economic, hospital or medication domains. Outcomes within the hospital domain comprise any resource use information related to inpatient or day-service hospital care (e.g., number of hospital admissions or length of stay). Outcomes related to medications include information such as number of drugs, daily doses. Outcomes in the economic domain are mostly general outcomes (e.g., cost, resource use) that is not captured neither in the hospital, nor in the medication domains. These include any other relevant resource use information associated to a given health intervention, such as personnel costs or intervention costs. Metrics related to societal/caregiver burden also emerge from the studies of our review, although less extensively.

Lastly, core areas of death – gauged either in the form of mortality rate, survival, or clinical remission – and adverse events – such as unexpected worsening of conditions – are also only marginally observed, although mainly as secondary endpoints, as proxies for intervention effectiveness.

Table 6 Outcome area, domains and measures

Core area	N. outcome	Top 3 outcome domains	Outcome measures
Life impact	82	Delivery of care	Satisfaction with care; Patient Assessment of Chronic Illness Care (PACIC)
		Perceived health status	Quality of life, via EQ-5D
		Physical functioning	Instrumental Activities of Daily Living scales (ADL); Short-Form 12 (SF-12)
Resource use	30	Economic	Administrative data, intervention costs, ...
		Hospital	Number of hospital admissions, length of hospital stay, ...
		Need for further intervention	Medication therapy and costs
Physiological/ clinical	30	General outcomes	Blood pressure, cholesterol, changes in levels of clinical parameters
		Psychiatric outcomes	Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression scale (CESD-10); Hopkins Symptom Checklist (HSCL-20) or "Depression-free days"
		Other outcome areas	E.g., cardiac outcomes or metabolism and nutrition outcomes
Death	6	Mortality/survival	Mortality rate, survival, clinical remission
Adverse events	1	Adverse events/effects	Variables of clinical efficacy, e.g., the number of episodes of worsening of the pulmonary and/or heart condition

Methods of Economic Evaluations of health service interventions

This review comprises 22 full economic evaluations (EEs). Full economic evaluations are analysis where both outcome and costs are analysed, for either the intervention and its comparator⁵⁸. Table 7 reports the main characteristics of the studies.

Cost-Utility Analysis (CUA) is the most common type of EE (87% of the studies). 3 studies conduct both Cost-Effectiveness Analysis (CEA) and CUA. There is no Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) or Cost-Minimization Analysis (CMA) in scope. The perspective of these EEs varies. 10 studies (43%) assume a healthcare perspective, whereas 6 (26%) studies combine a healthcare perspective with a societal one.

A pure societal perspective is taken from 6 (26%) studies. One study specifically assumes the perspective of the insurance payer.

In terms of outcome measure, Quality-Adjusted Life Years (QALYs) are the most used metric for utility levels. QALYs measure health outcomes accounting for both length of life (i.e., mortality) and quality of life (i.e., morbidity)⁵⁹. Most of the studies derives QALYs from the EQ-5D (EuroQoL[†]) scale, a generic measure for quality of life that is gauged with either 5 dimensions (mobility, self-care, usual activities, pain/discomfort and anxiety/depression) using either 3 (EQ-5D-3L: no problems, some problems, and extreme problems) or 5 (EQ-5D-5L: no problems, slight problems, moderate problems, severe problems and extreme problems) levels. The second most-used metrics for quality of life is the Short-Form 12 survey⁶⁰, a patient-reported outcome measure that assesses how health impacts on everyday life.

In terms of resource use and costs included in the analysis, Table 7 displays the costs broken-down across four classes: direct health care costs, indirect health care costs, intervention costs, and out-of-pocket (OOP) costs. Direct health care costs include costs associated to any health care event that implies healthcare resource use. This ranges from hospitalization, to medication, from Emergency Department (ED) visits to outpatient visits. Indirect health care costs comprise all costs paid indirectly to access a health service. These include travel costs, dining costs, patients' work leave, caregivers' work leave, and formal caregiver expenses. Intervention costs are costs directly sustained to implement the healthcare intervention being developed or piloted. These include but are not limited to development costs, training costs, staff costs, or trial costs. Out-of-pocket (OOP) costs are any other healthcare expense directly paid by the patient or their family, which is not reimbursed by the healthcare system. Some examples include non-prescription drugs, second-opinion visits, home care or community care.

Information on resource use is collected via different sources. Retrospective studies typically rely on already available data, including administrative databases, health insurance claims or extractions from the general practitioners' records. In addition, prospective studies, like RCTs or non-trial, observational studies, can also gather additional data, e.g., out-of-pocket (OOP) expenses, via patient-administered questionnaires. As far as the costs are concerned, resources are typically valued using officially listed prices from national or local formularies. Current prices are generally used.

Lastly, sensitivity analyses are often performed in EEs, to account for uncertainty factors and assumptions on which the analyses are built. In the selected studies, sensitivity analyses are performed in 13 (57%) studies.

†† <https://euroqol.org/>

Table 7 Characteristics of economic evaluations (EEs)

Author	Type of EE	Outcome measure	Direct costs	Indirect costs	Intervention costs	OOP costs	Perspective of analysis	Sensitivity analysis
Aragones, 2020 ²⁹	CUA	QALYs, using EQ-5D-3L	Y	Y	Y	N	Healthcare & societal	Y
Belnap, 2019 ⁴⁴	CUA	QALYs, using SF-12 scores	Y	N	N	N	Health insurance payer	N
Piera-Jiménez, 2021 ³⁰	CEA	QALYs, using the Barthel index scale	Y	Y	N	N	Healthcare & societal	N
Evans, 2011 ²⁰	CEA	EQ-5D-5L Crosswalk Index value	Y	Y	N	N	Not indicated (supposedly, societal)	N
Duarte, 2015 ²¹	CUA	QALYs, using EQ-5D-3L	Y	N	Y	N	Healthcare	Y
Thorn, 2020 ²²	CUA	QALYs, using EQ-5D-5L	Y	Y	Y	Y	NHS & Personal Social Service (PSS)	Y
Henderson, 2013 ²³	CUA	QALYs, using EQ-5D	N	N	Y	N	Healthcare & social services	Y
Maru, 2018 ⁴⁷	CUA	QALYs, using EQ-5D-3L; Life-years (LYs)	Y	N	Y	N	Healthcare	Y
Russo, 2012 ⁴⁵	CUA	QALYs (using a regression model based on vitals levels)	Y	N	Y	N	Healthcare	Y
Camacho, 2016 ²⁴	CUA	QALYs, using EQ-5D-5L	Y	Y	Y	N	Societal	Y
Nobis, 2013 ³⁵	CEA, CUA	QALYs, using EQ-5D and SF-12	Y	Y	N	N	Societal	N
Rose, 2015 ³⁶	CUA	QALYs, using EQ-5D	Y	N	N	N	Societal	N
Casanas, 2019 ³¹	CUA	QALYs, using EQ-5D-5L	Y	N	Y	N	Not indicated (supposedly, healthcare)	Y
Pedersen, 2021 ³⁷	CEA, CUA	EQ-5D-5L	Y	Y	N	N	Healthcare	N
Martin-Lesende, 2011 ³²	CUA	QALYs, using EQ-5D	Y	N	Y	N	Healthcare	Y
Bower, 2012 ²⁵	CUA	QALYs, using EQ-5D	Y	Y	N	Y	Not indicated (supposedly, societal)	N
Gray, 2016 ⁴⁰	CUA	HrQoL, using AQoL-4D	Y	N	Y	N	Healthcare & societal	Y
Herkert, 2020 ³⁹	CUA	QALYs, using EQ-5D-5L	Y	N	Y	N	Healthcare	Y
Johnson, 2012 ⁴¹	CUA	HrQoL, using SF-12 and EQ-5D	Y	N	Y	N	Primary Care Network	Y
Man, 2016 ²⁶	CUA	QALYs, using EQ-5D-5L	Y	Y	N	N	NHS and Personal Social Service (PSS); patient	N
Lanzeta, 2016 ³³	CUA	QALYs, using EQ-5D	Y	N	N	N	Not indicated (supposedly, healthcare)	N
Gillespie, 2017 ³⁸	CEA, CUA	QALYs, using EQ-5D	Y	N	Y	N	Healthcare	Y

Y = yes, N= No

2.4 Discussion

Summary of evidence

This scoping literature review was intended to build on the available methodology to conduct Economic Evaluations (EEs) of health service interventions, with a specific focus on multimorbid patients. The following section highlights both strengths and weaknesses emerged from the available literature.

Despite being still relatively limited in number of available studies compared to economic analyses of drugs or medical devices, this work outlines a growing academic interest towards performing economic evaluations of health service interventions and care programs, particularly with respect to chronic conditions. As chronic conditions typically emerge with ageing, we decided not to put any age-based constraint on our search with the purpose to obtain a search as comprehensive as possible. As a matter of fact, most of the studies on service interventions for multimorbid patients selected in our review implicitly involved a relatively old population (mean age is 63 years old in the selected studies). Most of the economic evaluation of health service interventions are full economic analyses, mostly cost-utility analyses (CUA), confirming academic attention on assessing that new care programs or patient pathways should be extensively assessed with an economic perspective, as opposed to only assessing their clinical effectiveness.

However, the distinctive features of service interventions – ranging from their users to their delivery modes – result in gaps in the methods currently used to conduct economic evaluations of health service interventions, therefore posing challenges to GERONTE’s economic evaluation. To begin, most of the economic evaluations available today are performed relative to single-disease centered interventions (e.g., COPD or cardiovascular disease only – excluded from this review). EEs deliberately focused on interventions for multimorbid patients are still scarce. As such, the need for further well conducted studies on the cost-effectiveness of interventions for multimorbid patients was observed and confirmed. Multimorbidity is yet assessed as a status that combines two or more specific and well identified health conditions, typically a chronic disease combined with a mental health condition (e.g., COPD and depression or anxiety). The number of EEs of health interventions specifically designed for oncologic patients with co-morbidities is extremely limited, let alone for health programs targeting geriatric patients with cancer. As such, the GERONTE model represents a unique care pathway in its ambition to take care of frail, older patients with cancer and various comorbidity profiles. Moreover, the GERONTE pathway also stands out as it aims to pursue integrated care by connecting a plenitude of healthcare professionals, coordinated by an APN, with a platform that comes in the form of a mHealth App for the patients. Conversely, there is a relatively limited number of studies where digital health tools, including platforms of apps, succeed in supporting the delivery of care for multimorbid patients while being integrated with different care settings or healthcare professionals.

Another weakness of currently available EEs performed in the area of service interventions relates to the poor generalizability of their evidence due to the strong role played by environmental factors where they are experimented and implemented. The effectiveness and success of a care program largely depend on contextual and organizational factors, and since service interventions comprised in this review are delivered – therefore evaluated – in specific care settings, the generated evidence results neither easily transferrable, not generalizable to other outside-study contexts. In this review, none of the studies paves the way to transfer their findings in other contexts.

Lastly, an analysis of the outcome measures gauged in studies of this review highlighted that, although the delivery of care domain is often monitored⁵², the overall patient experience with the intervention is scarcely extensively assessed. Most of the studies still uses plain, typically one-question-only scales that assess the overall satisfaction with the health intervention (e.g., “On a 1-10 scale, how satisfied are you with this care program?”). More sophisticated patient-reported experience measures (PREMs) do not seem to be yet systematically measured, nor monitored. Over the last decade, increased attention has been placed on measuring and improving the healthcare experience of patients. Patient experience is increasingly recognized as an integral component of service quality and positive patient experiences are associated with better adherence to treatment⁶¹ and thus with better outcomes. With GERONTE, we plan to fill this gap by assessing the patient experience with a 360-degree perspective, using questionnaires that more comprehensively evaluate the patient-centred, integrated care pathway. Figure 2 provides a visual overview of how the GERONTE project intends to fill the gaps identified in the literature.

Figure 2 Current gaps and the way forward with GERONTE

Current gaps	•GERONTE Model
Few studies on service interventions for older multimorbid geriatric patients	•Care model designed for older multimorbid geriatric patients with cancer as main disease
Studies mostly focused on combinations of specific diseases	•Involvement of comorbid cancer patients, with various multimorbidity profiles
Poor generalizability due to a strong dependency on contextual factors	•Economic evaluation and realistic evaluation to account for context/mechanisms/outcome
Patients’ experience with respect to the intervention is rarely measured	•Use of PREMs to take into account patients’ perspective and how it changes over time
Experiences with digital health tools (like apps) manily isolated	•Real time patient-reported data collection on an integrated data collection platform (Holis)

Limitations

The current work presents some limitations. First, the high heterogeneity of the interventions assessed in the selected studies, as well as their mixed target populations, limits the possibility to evaluate costs and outcomes of the EEs with a comparative perspective. For this reason, we did not deem informative to analyse the findings from the selected studies, nor to perform a meta-analysis.

A second limitation can be found in the fact that cancer populations are not appropriately represented in the research, especially in high-quality design studies (e.g., RCTs). Results should therefore be interpreted with caution when applied to GERONTE.

Moreover, this work only considered studies published in English as inclusion criteria. Other potentially relevant EEs might thus have been excluded from our analysis on a language-basis.

Lastly, we mainly used a narrative approach to present the evidence from this review, due to the conspicuous number of selected studies as well as their heterogeneity. As such, additional considerations might have been missed out because of the limited number of quantitative analyses.

2.5 Conclusion

To our knowledge, this scoping review represents the first attempt to rationalize the evidence available in the literature related to health service interventions for multimorbid patients, as well as the methods to conduct their economic evaluations (EEs), with the aim to highlight the related gaps. The randomized clinical trial that will assess the effectiveness of the GERONTE's pathway, as well as the within-trial EE that will assess its economic impact, aim to fill the methodological and conceptual gaps highlighted with this work. GERONTE is the first care model specifically designed for older multimorbid geriatric patients with cancer as main disease that will simultaneously involve diverse multimorbidity profiles. With GERONTE, a realistic evaluation will complement the economic evaluation, to ensure a greater generalizability of the findings. The full-scale patient experience will be assessed using Patient-Reported Experience Measures (PREMs) and how it changes over time. The evidence from this scoping review is intended to inform the protocol of the within-trial economic evaluation that will be conducted with respect to the GERONTE pathway.

This evidence collected and synthesized through this work was shared and disseminated in several occasions. Annex 3 reports in full the details of the dissemination activities associated with this work.

Deliverable 3.1 is the output of Task 3.1 "Literature review on the cost-effectiveness of service intervention for older multimorbid patients", and supports Objective 3 of the GerOnTe project "Develop socio-economic methods for evaluating the impacts of the implementation of the GERONTE intervention" and more specifically O3.3 "Develop a model to perform economic evaluation of complex healthcare services".

D3.1 was delivered as planned at M12 and is 100% completed. No other changes are expected in the future.

The evidence from this Deliverable is intended to inform the protocol of the economic evaluation (Task 3.2; Deliverable 3.2).

3. Bibliography

1. Barnett K, Mercer SW, Norbury M, Watt G, Wyke S, Guthrie B. Epidemiology of multimorbidity and implications for health care, research, and medical education: a cross-sectional study. *The Lancet*. 2012;380(9836):37-43. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(12)60240-2
2. Johnston MC, Crilly M, Black C, Prescott GJ, Mercer SW. Defining and measuring multimorbidity: a systematic review of systematic reviews. *European Journal of Public Health*. 2019;29(1):182-189. doi:10.1093/eurpub/cky098
3. Rogowski J, Lillard LA, Kington R. The Financial Burden of Prescription Drug Use Among Elderly Persons. *The Gerontologist*. 1997;37(4):475-482. doi:10.1093/geront/37.4.475
4. Moxey ED, O'Connor JP, Novielli KD, Teutsch S, Nash DB. Prescription drug use in the elderly: a descriptive analysis. *Health Care Financ Rev*. 2003;24(4):127-141.
5. Smith SM, Soubhi H, Fortin M, Hudon C, O'Dowd T. Managing patients with multimorbidity: systematic review of interventions in primary care and community settings. *BMJ*. 2012;345(sep03 1):e5205-e5205. doi:10.1136/bmj.e5205
6. Starfield B. Comorbidity: Implications for the Importance of Primary Care in "Case" Management. *The Annals of Family Medicine*. 2003;1(1):8-14. doi:10.1370/afm.1
7. Condelius A, Edberg AK, Jakobsson U, Hallberg IR. Hospital admissions among people 65+ related to multimorbidity, municipal and outpatient care. *Archives of Gerontology and Geriatrics*. 2008;46(1):41-55. doi:10.1016/j.archger.2007.02.005
8. McPhail S. Multimorbidity in chronic disease: impact on health care resources and costs. *RMHP*. 2016;Volume 9:143-156. doi:10.2147/RMHP.S97248
9. Zulman DM, Sussman JB, Chen X, Cigolle CT, Blaum CS, Hayward RA. Examining the Evidence: A Systematic Review of the Inclusion and Analysis of Older Adults in Randomized Controlled Trials. *J GEN INTERN MED*. 2011;26(7):783-790. doi:10.1007/s11606-010-1629-x
10. Comis RL, Miller JD, Aldigé CR, Krebs L, Stoval E. Public Attitudes Toward Participation in Cancer Clinical Trials. *JCO*. 2003;21(5):830-835. doi:10.1200/JCO.2003.02.105
11. Cebul RD, Rebitzer JB, Taylor LJ, Votruba ME. Organizational Fragmentation and Care Quality in the U.S. Healthcare System. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*. 2008;22(4):93-113. doi:10.1257/jep.22.4.93
12. Nolte E, Knai C, Hofmarcher M, et al. Overcoming fragmentation in health care: chronic care in Austria, Germany and the Netherlands. *HEPL*. 2012;7(1):125-146. doi:10.1017/S1744133111000338
13. Bruthans J. The state of national electronic prescription systems in the EU in 2018 with special consideration given to interoperability issues. *International Journal of Medical Informatics*. 2020;141:104205. doi:10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2020.104205
14. Berwick DM, Nolan TW, Whittington J. The Triple Aim: Care, Health, And Cost. *Health Affairs*. 2008;27(3):759-769. doi:10.1377/hlthaff.27.3.759

15. Peters MDJ, Marnie C, Tricco AC, et al. Updated methodological guidance for the conduct of scoping reviews. *JBI Evidence Synthesis*. 2020;18(10):2119-2126. doi:10.11124/JBIES-20-00167
16. Tricco AC, Lillie E, Zarin W, et al. PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR): Checklist and Explanation. *Ann Intern Med*. 2018;169(7):467-473. doi:10.7326/M18-0850
17. Arksey H, O'Malley L. Scoping studies: towards a methodological framework. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*. 2005;8(1):19-32. doi:10.1080/1364557032000119616
18. Lefèvre T, d'Ivernois JF, De Andrade V, Crozet C, Lombrail P, Gagnayre R. What do we mean by multimorbidity? An analysis of the literature on multimorbidity measures, associated factors, and impact on health services organization. *Revue d'Épidémiologie et de Santé Publique*. 2014;62(5):305-314. doi:10.1016/j.respe.2014.09.002
19. Divo MJ, Martinez CH, Mannino DM. Ageing and the epidemiology of multimorbidity. *Eur Respir J*. 2014;44(4):1055-1068. doi:10.1183/09031936.00059814
20. Evans CJ, Bone AE, Yi D, et al. Community-based short-term integrated palliative and supportive care reduces symptom distress for older people with chronic noncancer conditions compared with usual care: A randomised controlled single-blind mixed method trial. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*. 2021;120:103978. doi:10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2021.103978
21. Duarte A, Walker J, Walker S, et al. Cost-effectiveness of integrated collaborative care for comorbid major depression in patients with cancer. *Journal of Psychosomatic Research*. 2015;79(6):465-470. doi:10.1016/j.jpsychores.2015.10.012
22. Thorn J, Man MS, Chaplin K, et al. Cost-effectiveness of a patient-centred approach to managing multimorbidity in primary care: a pragmatic cluster randomised controlled trial. *BMJ Open*. 2020;10(1):e030110. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2019-030110
23. Henderson C, Knapp M, Fernandez JL, et al. Cost effectiveness of telehealth for patients with long term conditions (Whole Systems Demonstrator telehealth questionnaire study): nested economic evaluation in a pragmatic, cluster randomised controlled trial. *BMJ*. 2013;346(mar20 4):f1035-f1035. doi:10.1136/bmj.f1035
24. Camacho EM, Ntais D, Coventry P, et al. Long-term cost-effectiveness of collaborative care (vs usual care) for people with depression and comorbid diabetes or cardiovascular disease: a Markov model informed by the COINCIDE randomised controlled trial. *BMJ Open*. 2016;6(10):e012514. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2016-012514
25. Bower P, Kennedy A, Reeves D, et al. A cluster randomised controlled trial of the clinical and cost-effectiveness of a "whole systems" model of self-management support for the management of long-term conditions in primary care: trial protocol. *Implementation Sci*. 2012;7(1):7. doi:10.1186/1748-5908-7-7
26. Man MS, Chaplin K, Mann C, et al. Improving the management of multimorbidity in general practice: protocol of a cluster randomised controlled trial (The 3D Study). *BMJ Open*. 2016;6(4):e011261. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2016-011261
27. Wanat M, Walker J, Burke K, et al. Linked symptom monitoring and depression treatment programmes for specialist cancer services: protocol for a mixed-methods implementation study. *BMJ Open*. 2017;7(6):e016186. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2017-016186

28. Coventry P, Lovell K, Dickens C, et al. Integrated primary care for patients with mental and physical multimorbidity: cluster randomised controlled trial of collaborative care for patients with depression comorbid with diabetes or cardiovascular disease. *BMJ*. 2015;350(feb16 3):h638-h638. doi:10.1136/bmj.h638
29. Aragonès E, Sánchez-Iriso E, López-Cortacans G, Tomé-Pires C, Rambla C, Sánchez-Rodríguez E. Cost-effectiveness of a collaborative care program for managing major depression and chronic musculoskeletal pain in primary care: Economic evaluation alongside a randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Psychosomatic Research*. 2020;135:110167. doi:10.1016/j.jpsychores.2020.110167
30. Piera-Jiménez J, Daugbjerg S, Stafylas P, et al. BeyondSilos, a Telehealth-Enhanced Integrated Care Model in the Domiciliary Setting for Older Patients: Observational Prospective Cohort Study for Effectiveness and Cost-Effectiveness Assessments. *JMIR Med Inform*. 2020;8(10):e20938. doi:10.2196/20938
31. Casañas R, Martín Royo J, Fernandez-San-Martín MI, et al. Effectiveness of a psychoeducation group intervention conducted by primary healthcare nurses in patients with depression and physical comorbidity: study protocol for a randomized, controlled trial. *BMC Health Serv Res*. 2019;19(1):427. doi:10.1186/s12913-019-4198-7
32. Martín-Lesende I, Orruño E, Cairo C, et al. Assessment of a primary care-based telemonitoring intervention for home care patients with heart failure and chronic lung disease. The TELBIL study. *BMC Health Serv Res*. 2011;11(1):56. doi:10.1186/1472-6963-11-56
33. Lanzeta I, Mar J, Arrospe A. Cost-utility analysis of an integrated care model for multimorbid patients based on a clinical trial. *Gaceta Sanitaria*. 2016;30(5):352-358. doi:10.1016/j.gaceta.2016.05.002
34. Schmidt H, Boese S, Lampe K, et al. Trans sectoral care of geriatric cancer patients based on comprehensive geriatric assessment and patient-reported quality of life - Results of a multicenter study to develop and pilot test a patient-centered interdisciplinary care concept for geriatric oncology patients (PIVOG). *Journal of Geriatric Oncology*. 2017;8(4):262-270. doi:10.1016/j.jgo.2017.04.002
35. Nobis S, Lehr D, Ebert DD, et al. Efficacy and cost-effectiveness of a web-based intervention with mobile phone support to treat depressive symptoms in adults with diabetes mellitus type 1 and type 2: design of a randomised controlled trial. *BMC Psychiatry*. 2013;13(1):306. doi:10.1186/1471-244X-13-306
36. Rose O, Schaffert C, Czarnecki K, et al. Effect evaluation of an interprofessional medication therapy management approach for multimorbid patients in primary care: a cluster-randomized controlled trial in community care (WestGem study protocol). *BMC Fam Pract*. 2015;16(1):84. doi:10.1186/s12875-015-0305-y
37. Pedersen SS, Andersen CM, Ahm R, et al. Efficacy and cost-effectiveness of a therapist-assisted web-based intervention for depression and anxiety in patients with ischemic heart disease attending cardiac rehabilitation [eMindYourHeart trial]: a randomised controlled trial protocol. *BMC Cardiovasc Disord*. 2021;21(1):20. doi:10.1186/s12872-020-01801-w
38. Gillespie P, Clyne B, Raymakers A, Fahey T, Hughes CM, Smith SM. REDUCING POTENTIALLY INAPPROPRIATE PRESCRIBING FOR OLDER PEOPLE IN PRIMARY CARE: COST-EFFECTIVENESS OF

THE OPTI-SCRIPT INTERVENTION. *Int J Technol Assess Health Care*. 2017;33(4):494-503. doi:10.1017/S0266462317000782

39. Herkert C, Kraal JJ, Spee RF, Serier A, Graat-Verboom L, Kemps HMC. Quality Assessment of an Integrated Care Pathway Using Telemonitoring in Patients with Chronic Heart Failure and Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease: Protocol for a Quasi-Experimental Study. *JMIR Res Protoc*. 2020;9(11):e20571. doi:10.2196/20571
40. Steele Gray C, Wodchis WP, Upshur R, et al. Supporting Goal-Oriented Primary Health Care for Seniors with Complex Care Needs Using Mobile Technology: Evaluation and Implementation of the Health System Performance Research Network, Bridgepoint Electronic Patient Reported Outcome Tool. *JMIR Res Protoc*. 2016;5(2):e126. doi:10.2196/resprot.5756
41. Johnson JA, Al Sayah F, Wozniak L, et al. Controlled trial of a collaborative primary care team model for patients with diabetes and depression: Rationale and design for a comprehensive evaluation. *BMC Health Serv Res*. 2012;12(1):258. doi:10.1186/1472-6963-12-258
42. Miklavcic JJ, Fraser KD, Ploeg J, et al. Effectiveness of a community program for older adults with type 2 diabetes and multimorbidity: a pragmatic randomized controlled trial. *BMC Geriatr*. 2020;20(1):174. doi:10.1186/s12877-020-01557-0
43. Weber C, Beaulieu M, Djurdjev O, et al. Towards rational approaches of health care utilization in complex patients: an exploratory randomized trial comparing a novel combined clinic to multiple specialty clinics in patients with renal disease-cardiovascular disease-diabetes. *Nephrology Dialysis Transplantation*. 2012;27(suppl 3):iii104-iii110. doi:10.1093/ndt/gfr292
44. Herbeck Belnap B, Anderson A, Abebe KZ, et al. Blended Collaborative Care to Treat Heart Failure and Comorbid Depression: Rationale and Study Design of the Hopeful Heart Trial. *Psychosom Med*. 2019;81(6):495-505. doi:10.1097/PSY.0000000000000706
45. Russo J. Cost-effectiveness of a Multicondition Collaborative Care Intervention: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Arch Gen Psychiatry*. 2012;69(5):506. doi:10.1001/archgenpsychiatry.2011.1548
46. Shakib S, Dundon BK, Maddison J, et al. Effect of a Multidisciplinary Outpatient Model of Care on Health Outcomes in Older Patients with Multimorbidity: A Retrospective Case Control Study. Lazzeri C, ed. *PLoS ONE*. 2016;11(8):e0161382. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0161382
47. Maru S, Byrnes J, Carrington MJ, Chan YK, Stewart S, Scuffham PA. Economic evaluation of a nurse-led home and clinic-based secondary prevention programme to prevent progressive cardiac dysfunction in high-risk individuals: The Nurse-led Intervention for Less Chronic Heart Failure (NIL-CHF) randomized controlled study. *European Journal of Cardiovascular Nursing*. 2018;17(5):439-445. doi:10.1177/1474515117743979
48. Baynouna LM, Shamsan AI, Ali TA, et al. A successful chronic care program in Al Ain-United Arab Emirates. *BMC Health Serv Res*. 2010;10(1):47. doi:10.1186/1472-6963-10-47
49. Smith SM, Wallace E, O'Dowd T, Fortin M. Interventions for improving outcomes in patients with multimorbidity in primary care and community settings. Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care Group, ed. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*. Published online March 15, 2016. doi:10.1002/14651858.CD006560.pub3

50. Ferrara L, Otto M, Apro M, et al. How to improve efficiency in cancer care: dimensions, methods, and areas of evaluation.
51. Hines P, Mercury M. Designing the Role of the Embedded Care Manager. *Professional Case Management*. 2013;18(4):182-187. doi:10.1097/NCM.0b013e31828ef230
52. Dodd S, Clarke M, Becker L, Mavergames C, Fish R, Williamson PR. A taxonomy has been developed for outcomes in medical research to help improve knowledge discovery. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*. 2018;96:84-92. doi:10.1016/j.jclinepi.2017.12.020
53. Glasgow RE, Wagner EH, Schaefer J, Mahoney LD, Reid RJ, Greene SM. Development and Validation of the Patient Assessment of Chronic Illness Care (PACIC). *Medical Care*. 2005;43(5):436-444. doi:10.1097/01.mlr.0000160375.47920.8c
54. Rabin R, Charro F de. EQ-SD: a measure of health status from the EuroQol Group. *Annals of Medicine*. 2001;33(5):337-343. doi:10.3109/07853890109002087
55. Edemekong PF, Bomgaars DL, Sukumaran S, Levy SB. Activities of Daily Living. In: *StatPearls*. StatPearls Publishing; 2022. Accessed March 28, 2022. <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK470404/>
56. Baron EC, Davies T, Lund C. Validation of the 10-item Centre for Epidemiological Studies Depression Scale (CES-D-10) in Zulu, Xhosa and Afrikaans populations in South Africa. *BMC Psychiatry*. 2017;17(1):6. doi:10.1186/s12888-016-1178-x
57. Vannoy SD, Areal P, Unützer J. Advantages of Using Estimated Depression-Free Days for Evaluating Treatment Efficacy. *PS*. 2010;61(2):160-163. doi:10.1176/ps.2010.61.2.160
58. Drummond M. *Methods for the Economic Evaluation of Health Care Programmes*. OUP Oxford.; 2015.
59. Ferguson ND, Scales DC, Pinto R, et al. Integrating Mortality and Morbidity Outcomes: Using Quality-adjusted Life Years in Critical Care Trials. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2013;187(3):256-261. doi:10.1164/rccm.201206-1057OC
60. Ware JE, Kosinski M, Keller SD. A 12-Item Short-Form Health Survey: Construction of Scales and Preliminary Tests of Reliability and Validity. *Medical Care*. 1996;34(3):220-233. doi:10.1097/00005650-199603000-00003
61. Fortuna RJ, Nagel AK, Rocco TA, Legette-Sobers S, Quigley DD. Patient Experience With Care and Its Association With Adherence to Hypertension Medications. *American Journal of Hypertension*. 2018;31(3):340-345. doi:10.1093/ajh/hpx200
62. Bower P, Kennedy A, Reeves D, et al. A cluster randomised controlled trial of the clinical and cost-effectiveness of a “whole systems” model of self-management support for the management of long- term conditions in primary care: trial protocol. *Implementation Sci*. 2012;7(1):7. doi:10.1186/1748-5908-7-7
63. Martín-Lesende I, Orruño E, Cairo C, et al. Assessment of a primary care-based telemonitoring intervention for home care patients with heart failure and chronic lung disease. The TELBIL study. *BMC Health Serv Res*. 2011;11(1):56. doi:10.1186/1472-6963-11-56

64. Sutherland D, Hayter M. Structured review: evaluating the effectiveness of nurse case managers in improving health outcomes in three major chronic diseases: *Effectiveness of nurse care managers. Journal of Clinical Nursing.* 2009;18(21):2978-2992. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2702.2009.02900.x

Annexe 1: Key word search strategy

Search date	07/06/2021	07/06/2021	08/06/2021	08/06/2021
Search #	#1	#2	#3	#4
Database	Pub Med	Science Direct	EconLit	Web Of Science
Key words	((service intervention) OR (care pathway) OR (patient journey) OR (care program)) AND (multimorbidity OR multimorbid OR comorbidity OR comorbid OR (chronic disease)) AND ((economic evaluation) OR methods OR (cost-effectiveness) OR (cost-utility) OR (cost-benefit))	((service intervention) OR (care pathway) OR (care program)) AND (multimorbidity OR (chronic disease)) AND ((economic evaluation) OR (cost-effectiveness) OR (cost-utility) OR (cost-benefit))	((service intervention) OR (care pathway) OR (patient journey) OR (care program)) AND (multimorbidity OR multimorbid OR comorbidity OR comorbid OR (chronic disease)) AND ((economic evaluation) OR methods OR (cost-effectiveness) OR (cost-utility) OR (cost-benefit))	((service intervention) OR (care pathway) OR (patient journey) OR (care program)) AND (multimorbidity OR multimorbid OR comorbidity OR comorbid OR (chronic disease)) AND ((economic evaluation) OR methods OR (cost-effectiveness) OR (cost-utility) OR (cost-benefit))
Fields	Title/Abstract	Title, abstract, keywords	All	Topic (title, abstract, keywords)
Sorted	Best match	Relevance	Relevance	Relevance
Date	2010-2021YTD	2010-2021YTD	2010-2021YTD	2010-2021YTD
Article type	Case report, classical article, clinical study, clinical trial protocol, clinical trial: phase I, II, III, IV, comparative study, controlled clinical trial, evaluation study, journal article, multicentre study, observational study, pragmatic clinical trial, technical report, validation study	Review articles, research articles, case reports, mini reviews	Academic Journals (all)	Article, Review
Countries	All	All	Europe, North America, Oceania, Asia	All
# of articles retrieved	173	124	6	First 500 by relevance retrieved

Annexe 2: Workshops

Below the meeting minutes of the three workshops conducted with UBx, KUL and DIAK

Meeting Minutes			
Date	2021-10-19	Time	9.30 am-10.30 am
Location	Video-conference		
Meeting Objective	<i>Workshop with UBx to share the results of the literature review and get feedback on specific configuration of the French Healthcare system</i>		
Attachment	<i>Ppt presentation of the workshop</i>		
<p>Agenda of the meeting:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 9.30 – Introduction • 9.40 – Presentation of the results of the literature review • 10.15 – Discussion about the results and the distinctive feature of healthcare services in France <p>Some relevant points emerged from the meeting:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is important to stress that GerOnTe intervention will involve either an organizational and human resources management change • There will be (potentially) a lot of data connected with the project that need to be used at the maximum – great opportunity • There is a risk related to the fact that several professionals are involved in the project and in GerOnTe model – this is an opportunity but at the same time something to take into account in the economic evaluation of the project • It is important to adopt a system perspective for the economic evaluation of GerOnTe • It is important to understand in each clinical site and in each country who is the owner of the care pathway for oncologic multimorbid patients • There could an organizational problem, because each site should find a moment (beside the multidisciplinary team) where other professionals (e.g. GPs, comorbidities specialists) are involved • It is important to take into account the different institutional configuration of the clinical sites involved, some are teaching hospitals, others are cancer centres, other are general hospitals. It would be important to consider what is the impact on care pathways and costs • Data availability will also be a problem – important to perfume a feasibility study to understand what data available in each clinical site to mitigate potential problems in the future <p>UBx will put BOC in contact with Anne Jeffré a data expert from UBx to understand the data available at local, regional and national level in France</p>			
Attendance record			
Organisation	Name	Signature (in person only)	
BOC	Lucia Ferrara		
BOC	Vittoria Ardito		
UBx	Pierre Soubeyran		

Meeting Minutes

Date	2021-10-19	Time	2pm – 3pm
Location	Video-conference		
Meeting Objective	<i>Workshop with DIAK to share the results of the literature review and get feedback on specific configuration of the Dutch Healthcare system</i>		
Attachment	<i>Ppt presentation of the workshop</i>		

Agenda of the meeting:

- 2.00pm – Introduction
- 2.10pm – Presentation of the results of the literature review
- 2.45 – Discussion about the results and the distinctive feature of healthcare services in the Netherlands

Some relevant points emerged from the meeting:

- There will be (potentially) a lot of data connected with the project that need to be used at the maximum – great opportunity
- In The Netherlands we need to consider how to analyse out of pocket expenses in the economic evaluation analysis as this are really marginal
- Linking with the work conducted under WP1 and the identification of different multimorbidity profiles, it is important to consider the impact of the profiles in terms of paramedic involvement in the care pathway
- It is important to understand in each clinical site and in each country who is the owner of the care pathway for oncologic multimorbid patients, in the Netherlands for example the role of APNs is already well established compared to other countries
- There are a lot of data available at the local level, and national level, while few data are available for home care, that is why it is important to complement the data collection based on electronic medical records, administrative and claims data with data collected by the APN or the research assistant throughout the trial (i.e., data on out-of-pocket expenses, travel expenses etc.)

Attendance record

Organisation	Name	Signature (in person only)
BOC	Lucia Ferrara	
BOC	Vittoria Ardito	
DIAK	Marije Hamaker	
DIAK	Nelleke Seghers	

Meeting Minutes

Date	2021-10-20	Time	5.30-6.30 pm
Location	Video-conference		
Meeting Objective	<i>Workshop with KUL to share the results of the literature review and get feedback on specific configuration of the Belgian Healthcare system</i>		
Attachment	<i>Ppt presentation of the meeting</i>		

Agenda of the meeting:

- 5.30pm – Introduction
- 5.40pm – Presentation of the results of the literature review
- 6.15 – Discussion about the results and the distinctive feature of healthcare services in Belgium

Some relevant points emerged from the meeting:

- In Belgium we need to consider how to analyse out of pocket expenses in the economic evaluation analysis as these are really marginal
- In Belgium there are no private clinics involved in the trial and co-payment in limited (5-10% of total costs) and is reimbursed by the insurance
- The role of the APN can change in the three countries, this is something that we need to map and consider in the analysis. Their role can change depending if they are considered oncologic APN or Geriatric APN
- In the different centres it will be important to check how the APN is integrated in the system – what are the characteristics of the APN, what is their job description
- Apart from the APN also the paramedic team involved in the care pathway can change – check and map what is the role of Breast nurse, of psychologist and other non-medical professionals in the care pathway
- There is a great integrated and interconnected Electronic Medical Record in Belgium, a lot of data are available and information on costs can be found in the national nomenclature (Risif Health care system – to check for more information)

Some variables to map under T3.5 based on the interaction with KUL:

- Professionals involved: who, role, integration with other professionals, where are they working, what are they doing, when
- Clinical sites: institutional model (university hospital / cancer centre, geriatric hospital); internal and external specialties, "make or buy" model, service model (ambulatory care, day clinic, inpatient, consultations), Multidisciplinary meetings (when, who is involved, organization), APN

Attendance record

Organisation	Name	Signature (<i>in person only</i>)
BOC	Lucia Ferrara	
BOC	Vittoria Ardito	
KUL	Hans Wildiers	
KUL	Lien Degol	

Below the presentation that was used during the meetings

Bocconi

GERONTE

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE COST-EFFECTIVENESS OF SERVICE INTERVENTION FOR OLDER MULTIMORBID PATIENTS AND PROTOCOL OF THE ECONOMIC EVALUATION

Task 3.1 and 3.2

Lucia Ferrara, Vittoria Ardito
Meeting Diak - 19/10/2021

Part 1: Evidence from the literature review

Goals of the literature review

- Identify gaps in current available evidence on the performance of different models of health service interventions (both clinical and economic) [Gaps](#)
- Identify the methods to assess the average cost of care at patient level, together with patients' satisfaction, health outcomes (i.e. patients' reported outcomes and experiences), quality of life and cost-effectiveness of a patient-centered holistic health management system¹. [Methods](#)

Understand the basis to assess the cost-effectiveness of service interventions for older multimorbid patients

¹ Grant Agreement

Study design and search strategy

Study design: Scoping review

Database: 4 databases, Pubmed, Science Direct, EconLit, Web of Science

Search strategy: keywords to be included have been identified based on an exploratory search

Time frame: 10+ years (2010-2021 June)

Search result: 800+ articles retrieved

Keyword search
(service intervention) OR (care pathway) OR (patient journey) OR (care program) AND (multimorbidity OR multimorbid OR comorbidity OR comorbid OR (chronic disease)) AND (economic evaluation) OR methods OR (cost-effectiveness) OR (cost-utility) OR (cost-benefit)

Study selection

Inclusion/exclusion criteria

- Studies published in medium- and high-income countries
- Study designs: research articles and protocols related to observational studies, trials, ...
- Single service interventions (e.g. literature reviews were excluded)
- All target age, except for pediatric patients
- Multi-morbidity and care delivery through multiple settings as inclusion criteria

Rationale for final selection

We selected interventions targeting patients with at least two chronic conditions and delivered through multiple care setting (including digital channels)

We did not limit our analysis to geriatric patients only, as for most of the interventions addressing chronic conditions the mean age was relatively high

PRISMA Diagram

Identification: Pub Med N=173, Science Direct N=124, Econ Lit N=8, Web Of Science First 500 by relevance

Screening: Papers for title/abstract screening N=796

Eligibility: Papers for full text reading N=117

Final Inclusion: Relevant paper included in the review N=29

Duplicates removed N=17
Snowballing N=1

Characteristics of the interventions – based on type¹

Organizational-type Interventions	Patient-oriented Interventions
- 13 of the studies involve case management, coordination of care or the enhancement of skill mix in multidisciplinary teams in addition to delivery of patient care	- 13 of the studies include psychoeducational programs, as well as individual or group-based sessions aimed at enhancing self-management and self-efficacy

Takeaway message:
Health service interventions are often developed across multiple dimensions (e.g., nurse care manager that coordinates health care efforts, through digital tools for patient monitoring) therefore they cannot be easily clustered into a single dimension (focus narrative)

Characteristics of the interventions – based on type¹ (1/2)

Study	Intervention	Process output	Data analysis	Integrated care, deliv. CT & Telehealth	Home	Presence
Alparicio, 2020	Virtual geriatric care via telehealth					
Barra, 2019	CT-mediated integrated care model for stroke					
Barra, 2020	Stroke care model with decision-making tools					
Edmond, 2017	USA home assessment and care delivery in phone					
Evans, 2011	Patients care by community-based nurses, specialists					
Thom, 2020	Review of patient health with nurse, pharmacist & GP					
Henderson, 2012	Home-based care with a higher education nurse					
Moys, 2018	Home-based care with home care development NP					
Ross, 2015	Medication review by pharmacist & home care support					
Henderson, 2012	Telephone-based intervention based on patients self-management & phone contacts with the doctor					

Characteristics of the interventions – based on type¹ (2/2)

Study	Intervention	Process output	Data analysis	Integrated care, deliv. CT & Telehealth	Home	Presence
Barra, 2020	Interventional assessment providing remote-based interventions, including nurse, pharmacist follow-up					
Barra, 2017	Stroke and patient centered approach to the acute management of long-term conditions					
Henderson, 2012	Collection of 600 medication & monitoring device manager					
Johnson, 2012	Collaborative geriatric-led ambulatory response systems					
Moys, 2018	Training nurses of each disease with patient centered care					
Leone, 2018	Home communication tool for & hospital professionals					
Moys, 2012	Integrated multidisciplinary care model					
Gillette, 2017	How to conduct a GP-led medicine review with patients					
Alparicio, 2020	Home visits, group sessions program, case conferencing and care coordination					
Country, 2019	Management of drug treatment, and prevention of relapse					

Characteristics of the interventions – based on type¹

Study	Intervention	Psych-educational	Self-empow.	Self-efficacy
Barra, 2019	Stroke medication, increasing medication adherence, monitoring system			
Duane, 2015	Phone information on depression, defining psychological interventions and monitoring progress			
Moys, 2012	Enhance patient self-management, medication reconciliation, coordination, and continuity of care			
Canale, 2018	Enhance based on internet psychological treatments			
Nessun titolo	Web based self-help program to address diabetes specific aspects within patient systems			
Costello, 2018	Health services as chronic pathology of depression, therapy, leading to improve behavioral activation, self-efficacy and depression			
Fraser, 2017	Support with case and disease change, and psychological tools through an online platform			
Gray, 2016	Improve patient self-management and shared decision making between patient and HCP			
Moys, 2017	Education on depression, evidence based psychological treatments, patient progress monitoring			
Williams, 2020	In-home only, group sessions program, case conferencing and care coordination			
Country, 2019	Behavioral activation, lifestyle advice, management of drug treatment, and prevention of relapse			

Characteristics of the interventions – based on conditions

Conditions treated	N. studies	%
Diabetes (type 1 or 2)	12	41%
Cardiovascular diseases (HF, chronic, or acute, ischemic heart disease, other)	12	41%
Chronic conditions not explicitly identified	12	41%
Mental disorders (depression or anxiety)	11	38%
Chronic lung disease (COPD, asthma)	5	17%
Cancer	3	10%
Multiple sclerosis (multiple sclerosis)	2	7%
Hypertension	2	7%
Fragility	2	7%
Infectious bowel syndrome	2	7%

Very few studies on comorbid cancer patients

Most frequent chronic conditions involve cardiovascular and respiratory disease

Most frequent chronic conditions associated with other chronic diseases

Target depression associated with other chronic diseases

Characteristics of the interventions – based on HCPs (1/3)

Study	Intervention	GP	Nurse	Specialty	Pharmacist	Other	Core HCPs
Alparicio, 2020	Chronic Medication plan and depression						Yes (Nurse)
Barra, 2020	Health failure and depression						Third sector
Barra, 2017	Stroke and chronic diseases						Yes (Nurse)
Raymond, 2020	Diabetes and hypertension			Oncology nurse			Physiotherapist or Palliative care
Leone, 2018	Care with generic communication						Yes (Nurse)
Evans, 2011	Frailty with multimorbidity			Oncology nurse			Physiotherapist or Palliative care
Duane, 2015	Cancer and depression						HCPs (not well defined) Community HCP
Thom, 2020	Stroke or more chronic conditions						Yes (Nurse)
Henderson, 2012	Conditions among heart failure, COPD, diabetes						HCPs (not well defined) Community HCP
Moys, 2018	Cardiovascular disease or transfer for diabetes/hypertension/hypertension						Physiotherapist or Palliative care
Ross, 2012	Depression disorder, with diabetes or COPD and/or type 1 or 2 diabetes, with depression symptoms						Physiotherapist or Palliative care
Garcia, 2016	Depression and type 1 or 2 diabetes						Physiotherapist or Palliative care
Moys, 2012	Depression and type 1 or 2 diabetes						Physiotherapist or Palliative care
Ross, 2015	At least 3 chronic diseases						Physiotherapist or Palliative care
Alparicio, 2020	Diabetes, chronic conditions type 1, COPD, asthma, ischemic cardiopathy and depression						Physiotherapist or Palliative care
Country, 2019	Management of drug treatment, and prevention of relapse						Physiotherapist or Palliative care

Characteristics of the interventions – based on HCPs (2/3)

Study	Conditions treated	GP	Nurse	Specialty	Pharmacist	Other	Core HCPs
Williams, 2020	SD, depression and/or anxiety					Psychologists	Yes (Nurse)
McIntosh, 2012	At least 3 chronic lung disease						Yes (Nurse)
Shah, 2016	Two or more chronic conditions						Yes (Nurse)
Nessun titolo	Diabetes, COPD and irritable bowel syndrome						Yes (Nurse)
Gray, 2016	At least two chronic conditions						Yes (Nurse)
Henderson, 2012	CHF and COPD						Yes (Nurse)
Johnson, 2012	Depression and type 2 diabetes mellitus						Yes (Nurse)
Mar, 2016	At least 3 chronic conditions						Yes (Nurse)
Ward, 2017	Cancer and depression						Yes (Nurse)
Moys, 2012	Two 2 diabetes mellitus and 2+ conditions						Yes (Nurse)
Leone, 2018	At least two chronic conditions						Yes (Nurse)
Wilder, 2012	Kidney disease, diabetes and/or CVD						Yes (Nurse)
Gillette, 2017	Pulmonary Depression, diabetic and/or CVD						Yes (Nurse)
Country, 2019	Depression, diabetic and/or CVD						Yes (Nurse)

Characteristics of the interventions – based on HCPs (3/3)

Nurses are key figures in delivering health interventions, either as enablers for the service delivery, or as support for the patient. 20 studies out of 29 involve nurses, with 6 being nurse-led programs

Care manager is also key role in patient-centered models. 6 studies have this figure, in 3 of which it is assumed by specifically trained nurses, like cardiac or oncology nurses

Specialized oncology nurses are involved for cancer patients

The role of care manager is key especially to coordinate multiple HCPs involved in the care pathway

Characteristics of the interventions – based on service delivery

Study setting where service interventions are delivered:

Primary care (66%)	Hospital (34%)	Home care (24%)
19 studies (66%)	10 studies (34%)	7 studies (24%)

Community setting: 5 studies (17%)
Outpatient: 2 studies (7%)
Online programs: 2 studies (7%)

Hospital care is combined with home care (4 studies), primary care (2 studies), outpatient care, community setting and online programs (1 study each)

Digital channels are often involved in some part of the journey, in dual forms

- As a key component of the intervention (e.g., platforms for symptom monitoring, channels for real time, integrated communication)
- As a support (e.g., telemonitoring during follow up)

Characteristics of the interventions – based on outcome (1/4)

Core area	N. outcome	Top 3 outcome domain	Outcome measures
Life impact	12	Delivery of care	Satisfaction with care; Patient Assessment of Chronic Stress Care (PACSC)
Resource use	30	Perceived health status	Quality of life, via EQ-SD
Physiological clinical	30	Physical functioning	Instrumental Activities of Daily Living scales (IADL); Short Form-12 (SF-12)
Death	6		
Adverse events	1		

EQ-SD is the most common generic quality of life measure

- Specialist QoL is usually paired with a disease specific measure
- Patient satisfaction is commonly assessed, as opposed to the overall patient experience (PREM)

Characteristics of the interventions – based on outcome (2/4)

Core area	N. outcome	Top 3 outcome domain	Outcome measures
Life impact	12	Economic	Administrative data, Intervention costs, ...
Resource use	30	Hospital	Number of hospital admissions, length of hospital stay, ...
Physiological clinical	30	Need for further intervention	Medication therapy and costs
Death	6		
Adverse events	1		

Costs are measured either through admin. databases or through patient questionnaires

- Intervention costs (e.g. therapy costs or equipment) are typically considered in the economic analyses
- Out-of-pocket costs (e.g. over-the-counter medications) are not commonly measured

Characteristics of the interventions – based on outcome (3/4)

Core area	N. outcome	Top 3 outcome domain	Outcome measures
Life impact	12	General outcomes	EQ-SD (Nessun titolo) ranges in levels of clinical parameters
Resource use	30	Psychiatric outcomes	Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression scale (CES-D-10); Hepburn Symptom Checklist (HPSCL-20) or "Depression free day"
Physiological clinical	30	Other outcome areas	E.g. cardiac outcomes or metabolism and nutrition outcomes
Death	6		
Adverse events	1		

Physiological and clinical measures are often assessed as direct effects of service interventions, either as primary or secondary endpoints

General outcomes and psychiatric outcomes are the most common outcome domains

Results 19

Characteristics of the interventions – based on outcome (4/4)

Cost area	N outcome	Top outcome domain	Outcome measures
Life impact	42	Mortality/survival	Mortality rate, survival, clinical remission
Resource use	30		
Physiological clinical	30		
Death	6		
Adverse events	1	Adverse events/effects	Variables of clinical efficacy, e.g., the number of episodes of worsening of the pulmonary and/or heart condition

Some studies also include outcomes in the area of death and survival, mainly as secondary outcomes

- Adverse events, the unexpected worsening of conditions, can be used as a measure for intervention effectiveness (although not included in this review)

1 Core Outcome Set (COS) identification by Dool

Results 20

Economic evaluations (1/2)

- 25 out of 29 studies perform economic evaluations of the service intervention
- 22 full economic evaluations, assessing both costs and outcomes
- 3 partial, in the form of cost analyses or outcome description
- Costs categories most frequently measured in the economic evaluations:
 - Costs of health care services (e.g. hospital stay, outpatient visit, medications, ...): 92% of the studies
 - Intervention costs (e.g. equipment, personnel training, implementation, ...): 48% of the studies
 - Societal costs (e.g. productivity losses, caregiver time, ...): 36% of the studies
 - Out-of-pocket costs: 8% of the studies

Results 21

Economic evaluations (2/2)

- Perspective of the economic analyses:
 - Healthcare perspective: 46% of the studies
 - Societal perspective: 25% of the studies
 - Healthcare and societal perspective: 25% of the studies
 - Insurance payer perspective: 4% of the studies
- To account for uncertainty, 18 out of 25 studies conducted sensitivity analyses (72% of the studies)

Discussion 22

How to fill these gaps?

Current gaps	Way forward: Geronte
Few studies on service interventions for older multimorbid geriatric patients	Care model designed for older multimorbid geriatric patients with cancer as main disease
Studies mostly focused on combinations of specific diseases	Involvement of comorbid cancer patients, with various multimorbidity profiles
Poor generalizability due to a strong dependency on contextual factors	Economic evaluation and realistic evaluation to account for context/mechanisms/outcome
Patients' experience with respect to the intervention is rarely measured	Use of PREMs to take into account patients' perspective and how it changes over time

Discussion 23

Discussion:

- Do you know any other studies on comorbid cancer patients currently missing in this review?
- Any other aspects related to service interventions for multimorbid patients you would explore further?
- Any other questions?

Discussion 24

Next step: Economic evaluation of Geronte

Geronte distinctive features	Possible challenges
Service mode	Data availability
Strengths of existing outcome measures	Professionals involved
Weaknesses of existing outcome measures	Contextual factors
...	Differences among clinical sites
...	...

Discussion 25

Part 2: Building the protocol for the economic evaluation

Discussion 26

Protocol for the economic evaluation

Steps:

- Identify a minimum common dataset on cost information available at local level across the different trial sites (either administrative databases or to be collected ad hoc for the study) → with UBx, DIAK, KUL
- Identify unitary costs at patient level → reimbursement dossiers, with support UBx, KUL, DIAK **Today's focus**
- Establish how to combine costs and outcome measures → with MyPL
- Define tools for personnel and specific case report form items to collect data on cost from medical files

Discussion 27

Information to be collected at patient level

Resource consumption retrieved from each administrative databases:

- Hospitalization
- Outpatient visits
- ED admissions
- Home care
- Pharmaceuticals (inpatient and at home)
- Nursing homes or other HC facilities (e.g., territorial hospitals)

For each database, information on number of events, type and cost should be collected

Questions to address:

- Are these data available?
- Where we can find these info? (e.g. national health data system)
- Are these data uniform at national level?
- Useful contacts? (e.g., data availability, costs)

Annexe 3: Dissemination activities

D3.1 results were already presented in several occasions. Below the list of dissemination activities related to this Deliverable

- GERCOM084 & GERCOM093 Presentation of the Geronte project at a seminar at Bocconi University with researchers and professors as auditors; 2022-04-12 (FERRARA [BOC], ARDITO [BOC])

Agenda of the meeting

Da: Benedetta Pongiglione <benedetta.pongiglione@unibocconi.it>

Inviato: lunedì 11 aprile 2022 08:50

A: Rosanna Tarricone <rosanna.tarricone@unibocconi.it>; Claudio Jommi <claudio.jommi@unibocconi.it>; Vittoria Ardito <vittoria.ardito@sdabocconi.it>; Natalia Oprea <natalia.oprea@sdabocconi.it>; Oriana Ciani <oriana.ciani@unibocconi.it>; Lucia Ferrara <luca.ferrara@unibocconi.it>; Francesco Longo <francesco.longo@unibocconi.it>

Cc: Elisabetta Listorti <elisabetta.listorti@sdabocconi.it>; Aleksandra Torbica <aleksandra.torbica@unibocconi.it>

Oggetto: agenda workshop digital health 12 aprile h 12.30-14.00

Buongiorno a tutti,

Vi propongo una bozza di agenda per il workshop di domani. Il tempo riservato ad ognuno è indicativo e considerata l'ora e mezza che abbiamo a disposizione. Ho cercato di organizzare la scaletta in base alle disponibilità di tempo di ognuno. Fatemi sapere se vi ritrovate e può andare bene.

Grazie mille e a domani!

Benedetta

Agenda

- Benedetta Pongiglione (Intro) 5 mins
- Rosanna Tarricone/Claudio Jommi (Special Issue) 10 mins
- Vittoria Ardito/Natalia Oprea (ShareView) 10 mins
- Oriana Ciani (Cinderella) 10 mins
- Lucia Ferrara/Vittoria Ardito (Geronte) 10 mins
- Francesco Longo (digitalizzazione SSN) 20 mins
- Q&A discussione

Presentation 12/04/2022

1 ★

2

3

4

5

6

- GERCOM086 & GERCOM094 : Presentation of Geronte project at the Associate Cergas (Bocconi)- a network of managerial and professional operators of health systems, pharmaceutical and bio-medical companies; 2022-06-21 (FERRARA [BOC]; ARDITO [BOC])

Agenda:

21.06.2022

**Network Aziende Associate Cergas
SDA Bocconi**

**Come valutare gli interventi di
digital health?**

ORE 14:30 – 17:00

La sempre più pressante offerta di "strumenti digitali" per la cura dei pazienti rende necessaria una riflessione su come valutarli correttamente prima di adottarli. Come è stato già sottolineato, la metodologia di valutazione usata per i farmaci e per dispositivi medici non può essere applicata automaticamente a questo ambito. Come possiamo, quindi, valutare l'efficacia, la costo-efficacia o l'impatto sulla qualità della vita di questi interventi che ci vengono sempre più spesso proposti? Come comprendere se uno strumento che ci viene prospettato è stato sottoposto a un efficace percorso di valutazione?

L'incontro vuole provare a fornire alcune prime indicazioni attraverso delle esperienze di valutazione in corso, coinvolgendo i ricercatori che le stanno conducendo.

14:30 Benvenuto ai partecipanti
M. Cavazza (Coordinatore del Network Aziende Associate Cergas - GHNP SDA Bocconi)

14:35 Come valutare una mApp? Sfide e criticità
R. Tarricone (Cergas, GHNP SDA Bocconi e Dipartimento di scienze politiche e sociali, Università Bocconi)

15:05 Come valutare l'impatto di una mApp nelle realtà sanitarie? L'esperienza di Digital Health Solution Roche Smart Health Companion
V. Ardito (Cergas e GHNP SDA Bocconi)

15:35 Come valutare un intervento di telemedicina? L'esperienza del progetto Telion sull'aderenza e lo stato di salute del paziente con osteoporosi.
A. Compagni (Cergas e Dipartimento di scienze politiche e sociali, Università Bocconi)
B. Pongiglione (Cergas e GHNP SDA Bocconi)

16:05 Come sviluppare e valutare un RCT di un nuovo modello di presa in carico supportato da uno strumento digitale integrato? L'esperienza del progetto europeo Geronte
L. Ferrara, V. Ardito (Cergas e GHNP SDA Bocconi)

16:35:00 Q&A e discussione
17:00 Conclusioni

Presentation:

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

10

11

12

13

Project steps in a nutshell

Primary objective and endpoints: Improvement quality of life at 6 months after GERONTE inclusion

Secondary objectives and endpoints:

- Evaluate the effectiveness of the GerOnTe patient-centred system to:
 - Improve quality of life at 0, 3, 6 and 12 months (secondary endpoint #1).
 - Improve patient satisfaction and progression free survival at 12 months (secondary endpoint #2).
 - Improve patient autonomy at 3, 6, 9 and 12 months (secondary endpoint #3).
 - Reduce patient anxiety at 0, 3, 6 and 12 months (secondary endpoint #4).
- Reduce patient unplanned hospitalizations and patient readmissions at 6 months (secondary endpoint #5).
- Evaluate the efficiency of the GerOnTe patient-centred system through a cost-utility analysis (secondary endpoint #6).
- Evaluate caregiver burden (secondary endpoint #7).
- Evaluate patients, caregivers, physician and health professionals reported overall assessment of the GerOnTe system (secondary endpoint #8).
- Evaluate patient and health professional GerOnTe system satisfaction (secondary endpoint #9).
- Analyze the implementation and use of the GerOnTe patient-centred system by patients and professionals (secondary endpoint #10).

○ Analyze individual and collective barriers and facilitators to implementation and application of the GerOnTe system

○ Analyze the impact of the GerOnTe system on the evolution of practices and organizations at hospital

14

15

- GERCOM136, GERCOM137 & GERCOM 115: Participation to AIES Conference and presentation of Geronte; 2022-09-08 (FERRARA [BOC]; ARDITO [BOC])

Abstract AIES Conference 2022

How to conduct an economic evaluation of health service interventions for patients with multiple morbidities? A scoping literature review

Authors: Lucia Ferrara*¹, Vittoria Ardito¹, Valeria D. Tozzi¹, Rosanna Tarricone^{1,2}

Affiliations:

¹ Centre for Research on Health and Social Care Management (Cergas), SDA Bocconi School of Management

² Department of Social and Political Science, Università Bocconi

Corresponding author: Lucia Ferrara, lucia.ferrara@unibocconi.it, +39 333 1779591

Background and objectives: Patients with multiple morbidities have grown significantly due to population ageing, which translates in an equally exponential increase in healthcare costs and new patterns of resource utilization. Nevertheless, there is still a scarcity of economic evaluations (EEs) related to care programs targeting chronic patients. While methods to conduct EE of drugs and medical devices are well established, assessing health service interventions poses several challenges (e.g. difficulties in capturing all relevant data on costs and impact). This work is aimed at filling this gap and developing the methods to assess cost of care and patient outcomes, including quality of life, of patient-centred health interventions.

Methods: We conducted a scoping literature review of EEs of service interventions targeting patients with at least two chronic conditions and delivered through multiple care settings. We searched for articles published in English language between January 2010 and June 2021 on four databases, Medline, Science Direct, EconLit and Web Of Science, according to the following search strategy: [(service intervention) OR (care pathway) OR (patient journey) OR (care program)] AND [(multimorbidity OR multimorbid OR comorbidity OR comorbid OR (chronic disease))] AND [(economic evaluation) OR methods OR (cost-effectiveness) OR (cost-utility) OR (cost-benefit)]. Data extraction included the study overview, information about the intervention (e.g., target patients, care setting, number and types of morbidities, HCPs involved), and details from the EEs, including their type (e.g., CEA, CUA, CBA), outcome and cost measures, perspective of the analysis (e.g., healthcare system, societal), or if sensitivity analyses were performed.

Results: Our search retrieved 803 records. After duplicates removal, title/abstract screening and full-text read a total of 29 relevant articles were included for data synthesis. The EEs of service interventions currently available mainly refer to diabetes, cardio vascular diseases or depressive disorders. There is limited evidence on EEs on service interventions in oncology. Following the classification by Smith et al. (2016), the interventions were categorized as “organizational-type” or “patient-oriented”, and it was showcased that these health interventions serve simultaneously multiple purposes. On the outcome side, the majority of the studies assesses outcomes on life impact, such as quality of life, either with generic and disease-specific metrics. On the cost side, costs of healthcare utilization are analysed in over 90% of the studies, including hospital costs, medications, home-care, etc. Intervention costs are considered in almost 50% of the cases. Societal costs (e.g., productivity losses, caregiver time) are less frequently measured.

Conclusions: Despite the growing number of published economic evaluations of health interventions targeting multimorbid patients, our work showed that economic evaluations of interventions for patients

with multiple conditions are still typically conducted as the combination of different health conditions, rather than as an omni-comprehensive status. This makes it difficult to extensively map and measure the resource use and related costs sustained in every step of the care pathway, therefore making it harsh to estimate the overall cost of care for the health system or different pools of stakeholders.

Acknowledgements: This study is part of the Geronte (Streamlined **G**eriatric And **O**ncological Evaluation Based On **I**c **T**echnology For Holistic Patient-Oriented Healthcare Management For Older Multimorbid Patients) project, a Horizon 2020 European initiative funded by the European Commission (H2020-SC1-BHC-24-2020) aimed at improving quality of care for older multimorbid patients with cancer as dominant morbidity.

Program

Università
degli Studi di
Messina
DIPARTIMENTO DI ECONOMIA

AIES XXVII NATIONAL CONFERENCE

*“Sustainability and innovation in health: what challenges for
health systems and healthcare organizations?”*

Messina, Italy

8-9 September, 2022

Day 1

Registration (10:00-11:00)

Welcome to AIES Conference (11:00-12:00)

Keynote speech (12:00-13:00)

Light Lunch (13:00-14:00)

Parallel sessions 1 (14:15-15:15)

Parallel sessions 2 (15:20-16:20)

AIES annual assembly (16:30-17:30)

Social event (starting at 18:00)

Social dinner (starting at 20:00)

Day 2

Parallel sessions 3 (8:30-9:45)

Parallel sessions 4 (10:00-11:15)

Coffee break (11:15-11:45)

Parallel sessions 5 (11:45-13:00)

Light Lunch (13:00-14:00)

Round Table (14:00-15:00)

Closing (15:00-16:00)

Perception of telemedicine among patients with osteoporosis: a retrospective study (Pongiglione, Compagni, Mazziotti, Carrone)

Don't look up: trust and COVID-19 immunization choices (Carrieri, Guthmuller, Wübker)

Parallel sessions 4 (10:00 - 11:15)

Organizational models (chair: Guido Noto) – Aula Magna 2

Fostering the adoption and implementation of shared decision-making in breast cancer care: insights from a scoping review the lens of the implementation science (Oprea, Ardito, Ciani)

Le case della comunità tra disegno e sfide dell'implementazione (Del Vecchio, Giudice, Preti, Rappini)

Senza soluzione...di continuità (Monaco, Bellini)

Il precovero centralizzato-Centrale di programmazione chirurgica (Giuffra, Bellini)

Cost utility, cost effectiveness and HTA (chair: Alberto Ricci) – Aula 4

Methods and models adopted to conduct economic evaluations of health service interventions targeting patients with multimorbidities? A scoping literature review (Ferrara, Ardito, Tozzi, Tarricone)

Analisi dei costi a carico del Sistema Sanitario Nazionale relativi al percorso nascita: gravidanze spontanee e gravidanze da procreazione medicalmente assistita a confronto (Listorti, Torbica, Esposito, Franchi, Parazzini)

Integrating environmental sustainability HTA: the state of the art and possible trajectories (Bobini, Cicchetti)

Analisi dei processi di cura e micro-costing di 12 DGR pediatriche presso l'istituto G. Gaslini (Cavanenghi, Giuliano, Palmerino, Lecci, Furnari, Ricci, Zurlo)

Organizational models (chair: Anna Prenestini) – Aula 8

Public value co-production in Italian public healthcare organisations: evidence from a national survey (Oppi, Panella, Vagnoni)

Presentation

3. Results: Outcome (2/4)

Core area*	% outcomes	Top 3 outcome domain†	Outcome measures
Life impact	82	Economic	Administrative data, intervention costs, ...
Resource use	50	Hospital	Number of hospital admissions, length of hospital stay, ...
Psychological/clinical	30	Need for further intervention	Medication therapy and costs
Death	6		
Adverse events	1		

Costs are measured either through admin. databases or through patient questionnaires
 * Intervention costs (e.g. training costs or equipment) are typically considered in the economic analyses
 † Out-of-pocket costs (e.g. over-the-counter medications) are not commonly measured

19

3. Results: Outcome (3/4)

Core area*	% outcomes	Top 3 outcome domain†	Outcome measures
Life impact	82	General outcomes	Blood pressure, cholesterol, changes in levels of clinical parameters
Resource use	50	Psychiatric outcomes	Control for Epidemiologic Studies Depression scale (CES-D), Impairment Symptom Checklist (IMC-20) "Depression-free days"
Psychological/clinical	30	Other outcome areas	F.e., metabolic outcomes or metabolism and nutrition outcomes
Death	6		
Adverse events	1		

Physiological and clinical measures are often assessed as direct effects of service interventions, either as primary or secondary endpoints
 * General outcomes and psychiatric outcomes are the most common outcome domains

20

3. Results: Outcome (4/4)

Core area*	% outcomes	Top outcome domain†	Outcome measures
Life impact	82	Mortality/survival	Mortality rate, survival, clinical remission
Resource use	50	Adverse events/effects	Variables of clinical efficacy e.g., the number of episodes of worsening of the pulmonary and/or heart condition
Psychological/clinical	30		
Death	6		
Adverse events	1		

Some studies also include outcomes in the area of death and survival, mainly as secondary outcomes
 * Adverse events, like unexpected worsening of conditions, can be used as a measure for intervention effectiveness (although included in this review)

21

3. Results: Type of evaluations

- 25 out of 29 studies perform economic evaluations of the service intervention
 - 22 full economic evaluations, assessing both costs and outcomes
 - 3 partial, in the form of cost analyses or outcome description
- Costs categories most frequently measured in the economic evaluations:
 - Costs of health care services (e.g. hospital stay, outpatient visit, medications, ...) 92% of the studies
 - Intervention costs (e.g. equipment, personnel training, implementation, ...) 46% of the studies
 - Societal costs (e.g. productivity losses, caregiver time, ...) 36% of the studies
 - Out-of-pocket costs: 8% of the studies

22

3. Results: Type of evaluations

- Perspective of the economic analyses:
 - Healthcare perspective 45% of the studies
 - Societal perspective 25% of the studies
 - Healthcare and societal perspective 25% of the studies
 - Insurance payer perspective 4% of the studies
- To account for uncertainty, 18 out of 25 studies conducted sensitivity analyses (72% of the studies)

23

4. Discussion: Strengths

- Despite being still relatively limited, this review highlights growing academic attention towards the evaluation of health service interventions especially with respect to chronic conditions
- Most of the studies assessing service interventions for chronic conditions implicitly involve older patients (patient mean age relatively high in research articles with over 18 target patients at inclusion, namely 63 years old), therefore not restricting our search based on an age criteria allowed for more comprehensive results
- The vast majority of the studies on service interventions included in the review also performs a cost-effectiveness analysis, which are often CUA, pointing out to the growing importance in conducting an economic assessment of new care programs or patient pathways rather than just assessing clinical effectiveness

24

4. Discussion: Gaps in current evidence to address withGeronte

- Most studies on chronic conditions are still single-disease centered (e.g., COPD or CVD only)
 - Clear need for further well conducted studies on the cost-effectiveness of interventions for multimorbid patient
- There is limited evidence on economic evaluations of service interventions designed for complex multimorbid patients, even those specifically targeting geriatric patients with cancer
- Considering that the effectiveness of a service intervention largely depends on contextual factors, which differ between organizations, most service interventions assessed through this review are delivered in specific care settings, and their evidence is poorly transferable to other contexts
- While satisfaction with the service intervention is typically examined, a more comprehensive and structured assessment of the overall patient experience with respect to the care model seems to be often lacking, with PREMs not systematically measured nor monitored
- There is a relatively limited number of studies where digital health tools (like an App) are used to support the delivery of care for multimorbid patients in conjunction with other care setting

25

THANK YOU!
 CONNECT WITH US: info@geronteproject.eu
www.geronteproject.eu

26

www.GERONTEproject.eu

contact@GERONTEproject.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement [945218](#). The sole responsibility for the content of this project lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.